

Divisor Trek

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Abstract: Imagining that each divisor of the integers corresponds to a star in the sky, then here is Divisor Trek. If this study were a television series, then this would be the first episode. Divisor Trek is a journey along the infinity of divisors where we seek to demonstrate all the details and subtleties that have not yet been documented. It is the basis for a series of solutions that we will propose along the journey.

Keywords: Sieve of prime numbers; highly composite numbers; factors; pair of complementary divisors; fundamental theorem of arithmetic.

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“From the size of your little finger, you know how big the giant is.”

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1 Introduction

For this and other studies, we first need to make some conventions and notations. The most complete and up-to-date set can be found at “C000000 Conventions, notations, abbreviations, glossary, and references”[8].

1.1 Primality

Because of the conclusions on *Integers are only Primes and Composites*[9], here we consider the number 0 to be a composite and the numbers ± 1 to be prime numbers.

1.2 Sequence Direction

Any polynomial integer sequence has two directions.

This is the reason any polynomial has two recurrence equations.

So, if the direction is:

$$Yd[y] \equiv \{... e, f, g, h, i, j, k ... \} = \{... k, j, i, h, g, f, e ... \}$$

Then, the reverse direction is:

$$\backslash Yd[y] \equiv \{... k, j, i, h, g, f, e ... \} = \{... e, f, g, h, i, j, k ... \}$$

In our studies, if an OEIS sequence is $Axxxxxx$, then we write the representation of that sequence in the reverse direction as $\backslash Axxxxxx$.

1.3 Notation for union, interleave, and joining sequences.

We realized throughout the studies that it is necessary to make a distinction between the union, interleave, and joining of two or more sequences of integers.

We could differentiate interleave from union as follows:

- Union A with B doesn't bother to phase the sequences and doesn't bother to repeat common elements between the sequences. Union puts the same elements together and doesn't mind the lag between the sequences.
- Interleave A with B first puts the two sequences in phase, always at offset 0. Then you use the first element of A with index 1 and then you use the element of B with index 1, and so on. That is, A interleave B results in a different sequence than B interleave A. But in both cases the elements will be in phase. Interleave behaves like a zipper between the two sequences.

Notation for the union of sequences.

To denote the union operation, let us use the character “U”.

Being the infinite polynomial sequence $Axxxxxx = Y_1[y] \equiv \{..., 1, f, 3, h, 5, j, ... \}$ and a second infinite polynomial sequence $Ayyyyyy = Y_2[y] \equiv \{... 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 ... \}$, let us define the union of their elements while not maintaining the duplicity of the elements.

The denotation is:

$$AxxxxxxUAyyyyyy = Y_1[y] \cup Y_2[y] \equiv \{..., 1, f, 2, 3, h, 4, 5, j, 6, ... \}$$

$$AyyyyyyUAxxxxxx = Y_2[y] \cup Y_1[y] \equiv \{\dots, 1, 2, f, 3, 4, h, 5, 6, j, \dots\}$$

Example: the union of the sequences <https://oeis.org/A007590> and <https://oeis.org/A000982> result in different sequence from <https://oeis.org/A166515>. This new sequence does not have repeated elements. $Axxxxxx = \{0, 1, 2, 4, 5, 8, 12, 13, 18, 24, 25, 32, 40, 41, 50, 60, \dots\}$.

Notation for the interleave of sequences.

To denote the interleave operation, let us use the character “&”.

Being the infinite polynomial sequence $Axxxxxx = Y_1[y] \equiv \{\dots, 1, f, 3, h, 5, j, \dots\}$ and a second infinite polynomial sequence $Ayyyyyy = Y_2[y] \equiv \{\dots, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, \dots\}$, let us define the interleaving their elements while maintaining the duplicity of the elements.

The denotation is:

$$Axxxxxx \& Ayyyyyy = Y_1[y] \& Y_2[y] \equiv \{\dots, 1, 1, f, 2, 3, 3, h, 4, 5, 5, j, 6, \dots\}$$

$$Ayyyyyy \& Axxxxxx = Y_2[y] \& Y_1[y] \equiv \{\dots, 1, 1, 2, f, 3, 3, 4, h, 5, 5, 6, j, \dots\}$$

Sometimes there is no distinction between interleaving and union. Example at [C000663](https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/290564229267190/) <https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/290564229267190/>.

Example with distinction between interleaving and union: the interleave of the sequences <https://oeis.org/A007590> and <https://oeis.org/A000982> result in <https://oeis.org/A166515> where we keep the repeated elements.

Example for union or interleave resulting in the same sequence:

$$\a href="https://oeis.org/A052539">https://oeis.org/A052539 \cup \a href="https://oeis.org/A087289">https://oeis.org/A087289 = \a href="https://oeis.org/A000051">https://oeis.org/A000051.$$

$$\a href="https://oeis.org/A052539">https://oeis.org/A052539 \& \a href="https://oeis.org/A087289">https://oeis.org/A087289 = \a href="https://oeis.org/A000051">https://oeis.org/A000051.$$

Notation for joining sequences.

To denote the joining operation, let us use the character “+”.

Let us use this operation only to join the finite sequences and/or infinite sequences that have a first (or a last) element.

For example:

- Sequence 1 = <https://oeis.org/A056737> = A056737 = {0, 1, 2, 0, 4, 1, 6, 2, 0, 3, 10, ...}.
- Sequence 2 = number 0.
- Sequence 3 = <https://oeis.org/A063655> = A063655 = {2, 3, 4, 4, 6, 5, 8, 6, 6, 7, 12, ...}.

So, we denote the sequence $\{\dots, 12, 7, 6, 6, 8, 5, 6, 4, 4, 3, 2, 0, 0, 1, 2, 0, 4, 1, 6, 2, 0, 3, 10, \dots\}$ as $\setminus A063655 \setminus + 0 + A056737$.

2 The MID - Map of the Integers and their Divisors

When we highlight only the points showing the periods of the rows figured out by the periodic sequences $MHL[x, y] = x \text{ mhl } y = \frac{|y|}{y} + \left(x - \frac{|y|}{y} \pmod{y}\right)$ (see [12]), we get the figure in the XY plane:

Figure 1. [C000708](https://oeis.org/A000708) The points of the divisors in the MID - Map of the Integers and their Divisors. At each point, the X coordinate represents the value of the integer, and the Y coordinate represents the value of the divisor.

We will name this Figure 1 the MID - Map of the Integers and their Divisors[12]. MID shows us line by line the record of the divisor's values.

To produce the (x, y) coordinates of the points in this figure, we construct two tables. One table uses <https://oeis.org/A061017> and the positive divisors in increasing order <https://oeis.org/A027750>. The other table uses <https://oeis.org/A061017> and the positive divisors in decreasing order <https://oeis.org/A056538>.

Either of these two tables results in the same MID.

Since all the coordinates of the points are integers, then all the divisors of the integers are also integers. Whenever we mention divisors in this study, we are mentioning whole numbers.

Due to the modularity of MID's construction, all divisors are those that divide an integer and result in a remainder of 0. Equal to modular arithmetic. This becomes important when we analyze the infinite number of divisors of 0.

These observations are necessary when we verify that any Real number divided by itself results in the integer 1 and remainder 0. That is, all the numbers we know have at least one divisor belonging to the Real numbers that is itself.

2.1 Constructing MID with positive divisors in increasing order A027750

We divide this table into 4 pairs of columns, where each pair of columns represents the coordinates of each of the 4 quadrants.

In each of the 4 quadrants, the y-coordinate of each point is one of the divisors of the point's x-coordinate. All coordinates are integers.

Integers in Q1	Divisors in Q1 in increasing order	Integers in Q2	Divisors in Q2 in increasing order	Integers in Q3	Divisors in Q3 in decreasing order	Integers in Q4	Divisors in Q4 in decreasing order
https://oeis.org/A061017	https://oeis.org/A027750						
A061017	A027750	-A061017	A027750	-A061017	-A027750	A061017	-A027750
x	y	-x	y	-x	-y	x	-y
1	1	-1	1	-1	-1	1	-1
2	1	-2	1	-2	-1	2	-1
2	2	-2	2	-2	-2	2	-2
3	1	-3	1	-3	-1	3	-1
3	3	-3	3	-3	-3	3	-3
4	1	-4	1	-4	-1	4	-1
4	2	-4	2	-4	-2	4	-2
4	4	-4	4	-4	-4	4	-4
5	1	-5	1	-5	-1	5	-1
5	5	-5	5	-5	-5	5	-5
6	1	-6	1	-6	-1	6	-1
6	2	-6	2	-6	-2	6	-2
6	3	-6	3	-6	-3	6	-3
6	6	-6	6	-6	-6	6	-6
7	1	-7	1	-7	-1	7	-1
7	7	-7	7	-7	-7	7	-7
8	1	-8	1	-8	-1	8	-1
8	2	-8	2	-8	-2	8	-2
8	4	-8	4	-8	-4	8	-4
8	8	-8	8	-8	-8	8	-8
9	1	-9	1	-9	-1	9	-1
9	3	-9	3	-9	-3	9	-3
9	9	-9	9	-9	-9	9	-9
10	1	-10	1	-10	-1	10	-1
10	2	-10	2	-10	-2	10	-2
10	5	-10	5	-10	-5	10	-5
10	10	-10	10	-10	-10	10	-10

Figure 2. [C000708](https://oeis.org/A000708) The coordinates (x, y) of the MID points in the four quadrants using the sequences <https://oeis.org/A061017> and <https://oeis.org/A027750> (positive divisors of the integers in increasing order).

The sequence <https://oeis.org/A061017> gives the x-coordinates of the MID points. This is a sequence showing:

- The prime 1 is the only that never repeats in the x-coordinate,
- All prime numbers greater than 1 appear 2 consecutive times,
- All-composite numbers appear more than 2 consecutive times,
- All square numbers appear an odd number of consecutive times, and
- All non-square composite numbers, appear an even number of times > 2 .
- Whatever the finite number is, it is always a divisor of 0. That is, every division of 0 by a finite number always results in 0 with remainder 0. The number 0 is composite because if we were to show the table with the number 0, we would have to list it an infinite number of times. Since the 0 appears more than 2 consecutive times, then it is a composite.

Since for every finite non-zero number we have its negative number, then 0 has an even number of finite non-zero divisors.

Although the division $0/0$ is of indefinite value, whatever the finite result is, the remainder will always be zero.

If the division $0/0$ produces an infinite number, the remainder will also still be 0. This is because we cannot add any remainder other than 0 to a finite or infinite product to get back the number 0.

Because of the remainder 0, we may consider that 0 is a divisor of 0 itself with an undefined result.

To be more precise in the uses of mathematical terms, let us consider in this reasoning that:

- All finite or infinite even numbers are those that we can perform the bijection function with all its unit elements without leaving an element that does not have its corresponding pair. In this concept we can say that an infinite even number is one in which we can perform the bijection function with all its infinity of unit elements without leaving an element that does not have its corresponding pair.
- All odd, finite, or infinite numbers are those that we can perform the bijection function with all its unit elements, where there is always a single element left that does not have its corresponding pair. In this concept, we can say that an odd infinite number is one that we can perform the bijection function with all its infinity of unit elements, always leaving only one element that does not have its corresponding pair.

Because it is not possible to have a negative zero different from a positive zero, then 0 has an odd infinite number of divisors. This can be visualized by noticing that for every positive divisor of 0 there is always its negative counterpart. Because of the remainder 0, then 0 is also a divisor of 0 but has no sign. Then it is the only divisor that does not have its opposite sign pair.

This reasoning of thinking of the number 0 as having an odd number of divisors is in accordance with the class of square numbers. That is, just as the other squares have a finite odd number of divisors (starting in 1 with 1 positive divisor), 0 has an "infinite odd number" of positive divisors.

This means that, although it does not appear, element 0 is part of the table an infinite number of times.

2.2 Constructing MID with positive divisors in decreasing order A056538

This table is equal to the former table in Figure 2, but now for each x integer, the y positive divisors are in decreasing order.

Integers in Q1	Divisors in Q1 in decreasing order	Integers in Q2	Divisors in Q2 in decreasing order	Integers in Q3	Divisors in Q3 in increasing order	Integers in Q4	Divisors in Q4 in increasing order
https://oeis.org/A061017	https://oeis.org/A056538						
A061017	A056538	-A061017	A056538	-A061017	-A056538	A061017	-A056538
x	y	$-x$	y	$-x$	$-y$	x	$-y$
1	1	-1	1	-1	-1	1	-1
2	2	-2	2	-2	-2	2	-2
2	1	-2	1	-2	-1	2	-1
3	3	-3	3	-3	-3	3	-3
3	1	-3	1	-3	-1	3	-1
4	4	-4	4	-4	-4	4	-4
4	2	-4	2	-4	-2	4	-2
4	1	-4	1	-4	-1	4	-1
5	5	-5	5	-5	-5	5	-5
5	1	-5	1	-5	-1	5	-1
6	6	-6	6	-6	-6	6	-6
6	3	-6	3	-6	-3	6	-3
6	2	-6	2	-6	-2	6	-2
6	1	-6	1	-6	-1	6	-1
7	7	-7	7	-7	-7	7	-7
7	1	-7	1	-7	-1	7	-1
8	8	-8	8	-8	-8	8	-8
8	4	-8	4	-8	-4	8	-4
8	2	-8	2	-8	-2	8	-2
8	1	-8	1	-8	-1	8	-1
9	9	-9	9	-9	-9	9	-9
9	3	-9	3	-9	-3	9	-3
9	1	-9	1	-9	-1	9	-1
10	10	-10	10	-10	-10	10	-10
10	5	-10	5	-10	-5	10	-5
10	2	-10	2	-10	-2	10	-2
10	1	-10	1	-10	-1	10	-1

Figure 3. [C000708](https://oeis.org/A000708) The coordinates (x, y) of the MID points in the four quadrants using the sequences <https://oeis.org/A061017> and <https://oeis.org/A056538> (divisors of the integers in decreasing order).

The sequence <https://oeis.org/A056538> lists the divisors of the integers in decreasing order.

For example, in both tables for each integer $x = 6$ and $x = -6$, there are 8 points at the coordinates $y \in (\pm 1, \pm 2, \pm 3, \pm 6)$ or $(\pm 6, \pm 3, \pm 2, \pm 1)$. These 8 y -coordinates represent all 8 divisors for the integers 6 and -6 . They are all divisors of the integers 6 and -6 .

3 The square root of the integer numbers sifting the divisors of the integer numbers

To understand the unique hyperbolic and parabolic framework of the positive and negative divisors of the integers in the MID, we need to divide them into different sets.

All prime and composite numbers that are not square numbers have an even number of positive divisors. Only the square numbers have an odd number of positive divisors. This includes the prime number 1, and the composite number 0 explained above.

The square numbers are the key reference to begin the organization of divisors.

3.1 The pair of complementary divisors definition

We define $(d_1; d_2)$ the pair of complementary divisors such that $1 \leq d_1 \leq \sqrt{|x|} \leq d_2 \leq x$ and $d_1 * d_2 = x = integer$. In this definition we require only the positive divisors.

1. The divisors d_1 are less than or equal to the square root of the integer x . We will refer to these divisors as $d_1 = y \leq \sqrt{|x|}$. We describe them as two arrays in both sequences <https://oeis.org/A161906> and <https://oeis.org/A319135>.
2. The divisors d_2 greater than or equal to the square root of the integer x . We will refer to these divisors as $d_2 = y \geq \sqrt{|x|}$. We describe them as two arrays in both sequence <https://oeis.org/A340791> and sequence <https://oeis.org/A161908>.

The origin of the appearance of sequences in a duet where one refers to the divisors in ascending order and the other in descending order comes from the multiplication table result from HL - Hyperbolic Lattice grid[11]. This is because all products between two different integers have two forms of representation in HL - Hyperbolic Lattice grid such as $4 * 6 = 6 * 4$.

Only squares have a single distinct form of multiplication of two divisors where a product with two different orders of the divisors cannot exist.

For this reason, there are two pairs of complementary divisors arrays resulting in <https://oeis.org/A340792>:

$\begin{aligned} & \text{https://oeis.org/A161906} * \text{https://oeis.org/A340791} = \text{https://oeis.org/A340792} \\ & \text{https://oeis.org/A319135} * \text{https://oeis.org/A161908} = \text{https://oeis.org/A340792} \end{aligned}$
--

When we put all the divisors and their products in the XY plane, we get the MID - Map of the integers and their Divisors[12]. It is the lattice we get in the MHL - Modular Hyperbolic Lattice-grid using only elements $MHL[x, y] = y$. All other positions will be empty.

3.2 The pair of complementary divisors in MID

An immediate way to use the squares as our reference in MID is to divide the XY plane with the two parabolas $x = y^2$ and $x = -y^2$:

Figure 4. [C000708](#) The two parabolas $x = y^2$ and $x = -y^2$ dividing the divisors of the MID in the XY plane.

Here at MID is the same at FMT: all integers are produced by pairs of complementary divisors.

Usually, the representation of a point in the XY plane uses the comma to separate the two coordinates: (x, y) . In our studies of Number Theory, we will represent the pair of complementary divisors using the semicolon to separate its two divisors: $(d_1; d_2)$.

Also, whatever the pair of complementary divisors, always $d_1 \leq d_2$. There is no pair of complementary divisors with $d_1 > d_2$.

Now using the squares as our reference, the pair of complementary divisors is $(d_1; d_2)$ such that $d_1 \leq \pm\sqrt{\pm x} \leq d_2$, and $x = d_1 * d_2$.

- If the pair of complementary divisors $(d_1; d_2)$ is such that $d_1 \leq \pm\sqrt{x} \leq d_2$, then $x = d_1 * d_2 \geq 0$.

- If the pair of complementary divisors $(d_1; d_2)$ is such that $d_1 \leq \pm\sqrt{-x} \leq d_2$, then $x = d_1 * d_2 \leq 0$.

The product $x = d_1 * d_2$ are the points at X-axis.

The values of the divisors d_1 and d_2 are the values of the Y-coordinates of the points perpendicular to the X-axis.

Because of the symmetry in the multiplication table, we will always consider it to be just a single pair of complementary divisors when we exchange the sign of the two divisors of the pair. $(d_1; d_2) = (-d_2; -d_1)$.

Example 1: the integer $x = 6$ can be represented by the pair of complementary divisors $(d_1; d_2) = (2; 3)$ or by $(d_1; d_2) = (-3; -2)$.

- In the case $(d_1; d_2) = (2; 3)$, both divisors are in the 1st quadrant: divisor $d_1 = (6,2)$ and divisor $d_2 = (6,3)$.
- In the case $(d_1; d_2) = (-3; -2)$, both divisors are in the 4th quadrant: divisor $d_1 = (6, -3)$ and divisor $d_2 = (6, -2)$.
- In terms of pair of complementary divisors, we say $6 = (2; 3) = (-3; -2)$.

Example 2: the integer $x = -6$ can be represented by the pair of complementary divisors $(d_1; d_2) = (-2; 3)$ or by $(d_1; d_2) = (-3; 2)$.

- In the case $(d_1; d_2) = (-2; 3)$, divisor d_1 is in the 3rd quadrant at the point $d_1 = (-6, -2)$, and divisor d_2 is in the 2nd quadrant at the point $d_2 = (-6,3)$.
- In the case $(d_1; d_2) = (-3; 2)$ divisor d_1 is in the 3rd quadrant at the point $d_1 = (-6, -3)$, and divisor d_2 is in the 2nd quadrant at the point $d_2 = (-6,2)$.
- In terms of pair of complementary divisors, we say $-6 = (-2; 3) = (-3; 2)$.

3.3 The MID divisors in OEIS sequences

The MID pairs of complementary divisors may be positive and negative. They obey $d_1 \leq \pm\sqrt{\pm x} \leq d_2$, and $\pm x = d_1 * d_2$.

In OEIS we have the lowest positive divisors $d_1 = y \leq \left\lfloor \sqrt{|x|} \right\rfloor$ with the y-coordinates from sequence <https://oeis.org/A161906> or sequence <https://oeis.org/A319135>

We have the largest positive divisors $d_2 = y \geq \left\lceil \sqrt{|x|} \right\rceil$ with the y-coordinates from sequence <https://oeis.org/A161908> or sequence <https://oeis.org/A340791>.

3.4 The MID divisors in the MHL table:

We can build an equivalent table with the positions of all the MID points. In the points of the table that correspond to the points of the MID, we put the value of the Y-coordinate of the MID points.

Thus, in each vertical appear the positive and negative divisors of the integers on the X-axis. See the figure:

Figure 5. [C001431](#) The MHL and MID framework table.

This is the same Figure 4 showing the values of each MID point, as well as the MHL values. The MHL values are invisible in the MID.

The green and red values are the visible MID points.

The equal values of the central pair of complementary divisors of the square numbers are in red. The red points are those that are covered by the parabolas in the form of $x = \pm y^2$ in the MID in Figure 4.

4 The 5 sets of positive divisors

In this way, we can classify the positive divisors in 5 different sets:

1. [C000711](#) The divisors $y \leq |\sqrt{x}|$ which are the points $(x, y) = (A340792, A161906)$ with the increasing y-divisors labeled A340792A161906, or $(x, y) = (A340792, A319135)$ with decreasing y-divisors labeled A340792A319135.
2. [C000712](#) The divisors $y \geq |\sqrt{x}|$ which are the points $(x, y) = (A340792, A161908)$ with the increasing y-divisors labeled A340792A161908, or $(x, y) = (A340792, A340791)$ with decreasing y-divisors labeled A340792A340791.

3. [C000713](#) The divisors $y < \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$ which are the points $(x, y) = (C000427, A341674)$ with the increasing y -divisors labeled $C000427A341674$ or $(x, y) = (C000427, C000428)$ with decreasing y -divisors labeled $C000427C000428$.
4. [C000714](#) The divisors $y = \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$ which are the points $(x, y) = (A000290, A256958)$. We will name these divisors $A000290A256958$. These divisors are unique for each integer. There is no possibility exist the increasing or decreasing direction of these divisors for each integer number. This is the first quadratic sequence of divisors that appears.
5. [C000715](#) The divisors $y > \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$ which are the points $(x, y) = (C000427, A341673)$ with the increasing y -divisors labeled $C000427A341673$ or $(x, y) = (C000427, C000429)$ with decreasing y -divisors labeled $C000427C000429$.

The colors used for the divisors:

For divisors $y < \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$: #60497a or RGB (96, 73, 122)
For divisors $y = \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$: #FF0000
For divisors $y > \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$: #215967 or RGB (33, 89, 103)

Since for each integer the sequence of divisors can be increasing or decreasing, then it is possible to make two tables that represent the same relationships between these 5 sets.

Table I:

https://oeis.org/A061017	https://oeis.org/A027750	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snyp/posts/55948944684/	https://oeis.org/A340792	https://oeis.org/A161906	https://oeis.org/A340792	https://oeis.org/A161908	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snyp/posts/64385610507/	https://oeis.org/A341674	https://oeis.org/A000290	https://oeis.org/A256958	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snyp/posts/64385610507/	https://oeis.org/A341673
A061017	A027750	C000426	A340792	A161906	A340792	A161908	C000427	A341674	A000290	A256958	C000427	A341673
Integer	divisor	sqrt(x)	Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor
x	y	$\lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$	x	$y \leq \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$	x	$y \geq \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$	x	$y < \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$	x	$y = \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$	x	$y > \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$
1	1	1	1	1	1	1			1	1		
2	1	1.4142	2	1			2	1				
2	2	1.4142			2	2					2	2
3	1	1.7321	3	1			3	1				
3	3	1.7321			3	3					3	3
4	1	2	4	1			4	1				
4	2	2	4	2	4	2			4	2		
4	4	2			4	4					4	4
5	1	2.2361	5	1			5	1				
5	5	2.2361			5	5					5	5
6	1	2.4495	6	1			6	1				
6	2	2.4495	6	2			6	2				
6	3	2.4495			6	3					6	3
6	6	2.4495			6	6					6	6
7	1	2.6458	7	1			7	1				
7	7	2.6458			7	7					7	7
8	1	2.8284	8	1			8	1				
8	2	2.8284	8	2			8	2				
8	4	2.8284			8	4					8	4
8	8	2.8284			8	8					8	8
9	1	3	9	1			9	1				

9	3	3	9	3	9	3			9	3		
9	9	3			9	9					9	9
10	1	3.1623	10	1			10	1				
10	2	3.1623	10	2			10	2				
10	5	3.1623			10	5					10	5
10	10	3.1623			10	10					10	10

Figure 6. [C000709](#) The square root $y = \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$ separating (1) A340792A161906 the increasing divisors $y \leq \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$, (2) A340792A161908 the increasing divisors $y \geq \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$, (3) C000427A341674 the increasing divisors $y < \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$, (4) A000290A256958 the divisors $y = \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$, and (5) C000427A341673 the increasing divisors $y > \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$ of MID.

Table II:

https://oeis.org/A061017	https://oeis.org/A056538	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snyp/posts/360455948944684/	https://oeis.org/A340792	https://oeis.org/A319135	https://oeis.org/A340792	https://oeis.org/A340791	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snyp/posts/360464385610507/	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snyp/posts/360464975610448/	https://oeis.org/A000290	https://oeis.org/A256958	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snyp/posts/360464385610507/	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snyp/posts/360465238943755/
A061017	A056538	C000426	A340792	A319135	A340792	A340791	C000427	C000428	A000290	A256958	C000427	C000429
Integer	divisor	sqrt(x)	Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor
x	y	$\lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$	x	$y \leq \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$	x	$y \geq \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$	x	$y < \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$	x	$y = \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$	x	$y > \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$
1	1	1	1	1	1	1			1	1		
2	2	1.4142			2	2					2	2
2	1	1.4142	2	1			2	1				
3	3	1.7321			3	3					3	3
3	1	1.7321	3	1			3	1				
4	4	2			4	4					4	4
4	2	2	4	2	4	2			4	2		
4	1	2	4	1			4	1				
5	5	2.2361			5	5					5	5
5	1	2.2361	5	1			5	1				
6	6	2.4495			6	6					6	6
6	3	2.4495			6	3					6	3
6	2	2.4495	6	2			6	2				
6	1	2.4495	6	1			6	1				
7	7	2.6458			7	7					7	7
7	1	2.6458	7	1			7	1				
8	8	2.8284			8	8					8	8
8	4	2.8284			8	4					8	4
8	2	2.8284	8	2			8	2				
8	1	2.8284	8	1			8	1				
9	9	3			9	9					9	9
9	3	3	9	3	9	3			9	3		
9	1	3	9	1			9	1				
10	10	3.1623			10	10					10	10
10	5	3.1623			10	5					10	5
10	2	3.1623	10	2			10	2				
10	1	3.1623	10	1			10	1				

Figure 7. [C000709](#) The square root $y = \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$ separating (1) A340792A319135 the decreasing divisors $y \leq \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$, (2) A340792A340791 the decreasing divisors $y \geq \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$, (3)

C000427C000428 the decreasing divisors $y < \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$, (4) A000290A256958 the divisors $y = \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$, and (5) C000427C000429 the decreasing divisors $y > \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$ of MID.

4.1 [C000711](#) The divisors $|y| \leq \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$ in the MID

Using the sequence <https://oeis.org/A340792> for the x coordinate and <https://oeis.org/A161906> for the y coordinate, we construct all the points in the 4 quadrants for the positive divisors $|y| \leq \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$ in increasing order.

https://oeis.org/A340792	https://oeis.org/A161906	Q2	Q2	Q3	Q3	Q4	Q4
A340792	A161906						
Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor
x	$y \leq \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$	$-x$	y	$-x$	$-y$	x	$-y$
1	1	-1	1	-1	-1	1	-1
2	1	-2	1	-2	-1	2	-1
3	1	-3	1	-3	-1	3	-1
4	1	-4	1	-4	-1	4	-1
4	2	-4	2	-4	-2	4	-2
5	1	-5	1	-5	-1	5	-1
6	1	-6	1	-6	-1	6	-1
6	2	-6	2	-6	-2	6	-2
7	1	-7	1	-7	-1	7	-1
8	1	-8	1	-8	-1	8	-1
8	2	-8	2	-8	-2	8	-2
9	1	-9	1	-9	-1	9	-1
9	3	-9	3	-9	-3	9	-3
10	1	-10	1	-10	-1	10	-1
10	2	-10	2	-10	-2	10	-2

Figure 8. [C000711](#) The coordinates of the divisors $|y| \leq \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$ in the 4 quadrants. Positive divisors in increasing order.

Using the sequence <https://oeis.org/A340792> for the x coordinate and <https://oeis.org/A319135> for the y coordinate, we construct all the points in the 4 quadrants for the positive divisors $|y| \leq \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$ in decreasing order.

https://oeis.org/A340792	https://oeis.org/A319135	Q2	Q2	Q3	Q3	Q4	Q4
A340792	A319135						
Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor
x	$y \leq \lfloor \sqrt{x} \rfloor$	$-x$	y	$-x$	$-y$	x	$-y$
1	1	-1	1	-1	-1	1	-1
2	1	-2	1	-2	-1	2	-1
3	1	-3	1	-3	-1	3	-1
4	2	-4	2	-4	-2	4	-2
4	1	-4	1	-4	-1	4	-1
5	1	-5	1	-5	-1	5	-1
6	2	-6	2	-6	-2	6	-2
6	1	-6	1	-6	-1	6	-1
7	1	-7	1	-7	-1	7	-1
8	2	-8	2	-8	-2	8	-2
8	1	-8	1	-8	-1	8	-1
9	3	-9	3	-9	-3	9	-3

9	1	-9	1	-9	-1	9	-1
10	2	-10	2	-10	-2	10	-2
10	1	-10	1	-10	-1	10	-1

Figure 9. [C000711](#) The coordinates of the divisors $|y| \leq |\sqrt{x}|$ in the 4 quadrants. Positive divisors in decreasing order.

Figure 10. [C000711](#) The points of the divisors $|y| \leq |\sqrt{x}|$ in the 4 quadrants of the XY plane.

4.2 [C000712](#) The divisors $|y| \geq |\sqrt{x}|$ in the MID

Using the sequence <https://oeis.org/A340792> for the x coordinate and <https://oeis.org/A161908> for the y coordinate, we construct all the points in the 4 quadrants for the positive divisors $|y| \geq |\sqrt{x}|$ in increasing order.

https://oeis.org/A340792	https://oeis.org/A161908	Q2	Q2	Q3	Q3	Q4	Q4
A340792	A161908	Integer	Divisor	Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor
x	$y \geq \sqrt{x} $	-x	y	-x	-y	x	-y
1	1	-1	1	-1	-1	1	-1
2	2	-2	2	-2	-2	2	-2
3	3	-3	3	-3	-3	3	-3
4	2	-4	2	-4	-2	4	-2
4	4	-4	4	-4	-4	4	-4
5	5	-5	5	-5	-5	5	-5
6	3	-6	3	-6	-3	6	-3
6	6	-6	6	-6	-6	6	-6

7	7	-7	7	-7	-7	7	-7
8	4	-8	4	-8	-4	8	-4
8	8	-8	8	-8	-8	8	-8
9	3	-9	3	-9	-3	9	-3
9	9	-9	9	-9	-9	9	-9
10	5	-10	5	-10	-5	10	-5
10	10	-10	10	-10	-10	10	-10

Figure 11. [C000712](#) The coordinates of the divisors $|y| \geq |\sqrt{x}|$ in the 4 quadrants. Positive divisors in increasing order.

Using the sequence <https://oeis.org/A340792> for the x coordinate and <https://oeis.org/A340791> for the y coordinate, we construct all the points in the 4 quadrants for the positive divisors $|y| \geq |\sqrt{x}|$ in decreasing order.

https://oeis.org/A340792	https://oeis.org/A340791	Q2	Q2	Q3	Q3	Q4	Q4
Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor
x	$y \geq \sqrt{x} $	$-x$	y	$-x$	$-y$	x	$-y$
A340792	A340791						
1	1	-1	1	-1	-1	1	-1
2	2	-2	2	-2	-2	2	-2
3	3	-3	3	-3	-3	3	-3
4	4	-4	4	-4	-4	4	-4
4	2	-4	2	-4	-2	4	-2
5	5	-5	5	-5	-5	5	-5
6	6	-6	6	-6	-6	6	-6
6	3	-6	3	-6	-3	6	-3
7	7	-7	7	-7	-7	7	-7
8	8	-8	8	-8	-8	8	-8
8	4	-8	4	-8	-4	8	-4
9	9	-9	9	-9	-9	9	-9
9	3	-9	3	-9	-3	9	-3
10	10	-10	10	-10	-10	10	-10
10	5	-10	5	-10	-5	10	-5

Figure 12. [C000712](#) The coordinates of the divisors $|y| \geq |\sqrt{x}|$ in the 4 quadrants. Positive divisors in decreasing order.

Figure 13. [C000712](#) The points of the divisors $|y| \geq \sqrt{x}$ in the 4 quadrants of the XY plane.

4.3 [C000713](#) The divisors $|y| < \sqrt{x}$ in the MID

Using the sequence [C000427](#) for the x coordinate and <https://oeis.org/A341674> for the y coordinate, we construct all the points in the 4 quadrants for the positive divisors $|y| < \sqrt{x}$ in increasing order.

https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/360464385610507/	https://oeis.org/A341674	Q2	Q2	Q3	Q3	Q4	Q4
C000427	A341674						
Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor
x	$y < \sqrt{x}$	$-x$	y	$-x$	$-y$	x	$-y$
2	1	-2	1	-2	-1	2	-1
3	1	-3	1	-3	-1	3	-1
4	1	-4	1	-4	-1	4	-1
5	1	-5	1	-5	-1	5	-1
6	1	-6	1	-6	-1	6	-1
6	2	-6	2	-6	-2	6	-2
7	1	-7	1	-7	-1	7	-1
8	1	-8	1	-8	-1	8	-1
8	2	-8	2	-8	-2	8	-2
9	1	-9	1	-9	-1	9	-1
10	1	-10	1	-10	-1	10	-1
10	2	-10	2	-10	-2	10	-2

Figure 14. [C000713](#) The coordinates of the divisors $y < \sqrt{x}$ in the 4 quadrants. Positive divisors in increasing order.

Using the sequence [C000427](#) for the x coordinate and [C000428](#) for the y coordinate, we construct all the points in the 4 quadrants for the positive divisors $|y| < |\sqrt{x}|$ in decreasing order.

https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/360464385610507/	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/360464975610448/	Q2	Q2	Q3	Q3	Q4	Q4
C000427	C000428	Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor
x	$y < \sqrt{x} $	-x	y	-x	-y	x	-y
2	1	-2	1	-2	-1	2	-1
3	1	-3	1	-3	-1	3	-1
4	1	-4	1	-4	-1	4	-1
5	1	-5	1	-5	-1	5	-1
6	2	-6	2	-6	-2	6	-2
6	1	-6	1	-6	-1	6	-1
7	1	-7	1	-7	-1	7	-1
8	2	-8	2	-8	-2	8	-2
8	1	-8	1	-8	-1	8	-1
9	1	-9	1	-9	-1	9	-1
10	2	-10	2	-10	-2	10	-2
10	1	-10	1	-10	-1	10	-1

Figure 15. [C000713](#) The coordinates of the divisors $|y| < |\sqrt{x}|$ in the 4 quadrants. Positive divisors in decreasing order.

Figure 16. [C000713](#) The points of the divisors $|y| < |\sqrt{x}|$ in the 4 quadrants of the XY plane.

4.4 [C000714](#) The divisors $|y| = |\sqrt{x}|$ in the MID

Using the sequence <https://oeis.org/A000290> for the x coordinate and <https://oeis.org/A256958> for the y coordinate, we construct all the points of the divisors $|y| = |\sqrt{x}|$ in the 4 quadrants.

There is no increasing or decreasing divisors sequence since every square integer has only one divisor in the form of $|y| = |\sqrt{x}|$.

https://oeis.org/A000290	https://oeis.org/A256958	Q2	Q2	Q3	Q3	Q4	Q4
A000290	A256958						
Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor
x	$y = \sqrt{x}$	$-x$	y	$-x$	$-y$	x	$-y$
1	1	-1	1	-1	-1	1	-1
4	2	-4	2	-4	-2	4	-2
9	3	-9	3	-9	-3	9	-3
16	4	-16	4	-16	-4	16	-4
25	5	-25	5	-25	-5	25	-5
36	6	-36	6	-36	-6	36	-6
49	7	-49	7	-49	-7	49	-7
64	8	-64	8	-64	-8	64	-8
81	9	-81	9	-81	-9	81	-9
100	10	-100	10	-100	-10	100	-10
121	11	-121	11	-121	-11	121	-11

Figure 17. [C000714](#) The coordinates of the divisors $|y| = |\sqrt{x}|$ in the 4 quadrants.

Figure 18. [C000714](#) The points of the divisors $|y| = |\sqrt{x}|$ in the 4 quadrants of the XY plane.

4.5 [C000715](#) The divisors $y > \sqrt{x}$ in the MID

Using the sequence [C000427](#) for the x coordinate and <https://oeis.org/A341673> for the y coordinate, we construct all the points in the 4 quadrants for the positive divisors $|y| > |\sqrt{x}|$ in increasing order.

https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/360464385610507/	https://oeis.org/A341673	Q2	Q2	Q3	Q3	Q4	Q4
C000427	A341673						
Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor
x	$y > \sqrt{x}$	$-x$	y	$-x$	$-y$	x	$-y$
2	2	-2	2	-2	-2	2	-2
3	3	-3	3	-3	-3	3	-3
4	4	-4	4	-4	-4	4	-4
5	5	-5	5	-5	-5	5	-5
6	3	-6	3	-6	-3	6	-3
6	6	-6	6	-6	-6	6	-6
7	7	-7	7	-7	-7	7	-7
8	4	-8	4	-8	-4	8	-4
8	8	-8	8	-8	-8	8	-8
9	9	-9	9	-9	-9	9	-9
10	5	-10	5	-10	-5	10	-5
10	10	-10	10	-10	-10	10	-10

Figure 19. [C000715](#) The coordinates of the divisors $|y| > |\sqrt{x}|$ in the 4 quadrants. Positive divisors in increasing order.

Using the sequence [C000427](#) for the x coordinate and [C000429](#) for the y coordinate, we construct all the points in the 4 quadrants for the positive divisors $|y| > |\sqrt{x}|$ in decreasing order.

https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/360464385610507/	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/360465238943755/	Q2	Q2	Q3	Q3	Q4	Q4
C000427	C000429						
Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor	Integer	divisor
x	$y > \sqrt{x}$	$-x$	y	$-x$	$-y$	x	$-y$
2	2	-2	2	-2	-2	2	-2
3	3	-3	3	-3	-3	3	-3
4	4	-4	4	-4	-4	4	-4
5	5	-5	5	-5	-5	5	-5
6	6	-6	6	-6	-6	6	-6
6	3	-6	3	-6	-3	6	-3
7	7	-7	7	-7	-7	7	-7
8	8	-8	8	-8	-8	8	-8
8	4	-8	4	-8	-4	8	-4
9	9	-9	9	-9	-9	9	-9
10	10	-10	10	-10	-10	10	-10
10	5	-10	5	-10	-5	10	-5

Figure 20. [C000715](#) The coordinates of the divisors $|y| > |\sqrt{x}|$ in the 4 quadrants. Positive divisors in decreasing order.

Figure 21. [C000715](#) The points of the divisors $|y| > \sqrt{|x|}$ in the 4 quadrants of the XY plane.

5 C000710 The pairs of complementary divisors

Since MID is over the MHL - Modular Hyperbolic Lattice grid, then the X-axis stands for the values of the integers, and the Y-axis stands for the values of their divisors.

The separation threshold between the divisors of any integer x are the points $(\pm y^2, y)$ in red color. They form the two parabolas $x = \pm y^2$, or $y = \pm\sqrt{\pm x}$, in red.

The pair of complementary divisors is the pair $(d_1; d_2)$ such as $d_1 \leq d_2$ and $d_1 * d_2 = x = integer$.

Because of the negative and positive integers x , d_1 and/or d_2 may be positive or negative. The only requirement is $d_1 \leq d_2$.

In this sense, the only certainty we have is that for $x > 1$, d_1 is never equal to x and that d_2 is never equal to 1 or $d_1 < x$ and $d_2 > 1$.

Given $(d_1; d_2)$ a pair of complementary divisors such that $d_1 \leq d_2$ and $d_1 * d_2 = x = integer$, when d_1 increases, then d_2 must decrease, and vice versa. This is the hyperbolic effect that propagates through all integers, which we demonstrate in C002821 The Hyperbolic Framework of MID (link).

Because of the hyperbolic effect, for positive integers using positive divisors we must write the multiplication of pairs of complementary divisors in 2 sets of arrays:

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{https://oeis.org/A161906} * \text{https://oeis.org/A340791} = \text{https://oeis.org/A340792} \\ &\text{https://oeis.org/A319135} * \text{https://oeis.org/A161908} = \text{https://oeis.org/A340792} \end{aligned}$$

But also, is true to write the multiplication of pairs of complementary divisors for positive integers using negative divisors:

$$-\text{https://oeis.org/A161906} * -\text{https://oeis.org/A340791} = \text{https://oeis.org/A340792}$$

$$-\text{https://oeis.org/A319135} * -\text{https://oeis.org/A161908} = \text{https://oeis.org/A340792}$$

On the negative side of the X-axis, we can write the multiplication of pairs of complementary divisors array in Q3 and Q2 as:

$$-\text{https://oeis.org/A161906} * \text{https://oeis.org/A340791} = -\text{https://oeis.org/A340792}$$

$$-\text{https://oeis.org/A319135} * \text{https://oeis.org/A161908} = -\text{https://oeis.org/A340792}$$

Or

$$-\text{https://oeis.org/A340791} * \text{https://oeis.org/A161906} = -\text{https://oeis.org/A340792}$$

$$-\text{https://oeis.org/A161908} * \text{https://oeis.org/A319135} = -\text{https://oeis.org/A340792}$$

The particular care we take is always to respect the requirement $d_1 \leq d_2$ and $x = d_1 * d_2$.

Figure 22. [C000710](#) The mechanism of how complementary divisor pairs work for the positive, negative integers and zero.

The only integer numbers with repeated divisors (in absolute values) in the arrays are the positive and negative square numbers. These divisors are the only divisors that are covered by the two parabolas $x = \pm y^2$.

They belong to the two pairs of complementary divisors arrays:

- The pair of complementary divisors arrays <https://oeis.org/A161906> and <https://oeis.org/A340791>, and
- The pair of complementary divisors arrays <https://oeis.org/A319135> and <https://oeis.org/A161908>.

The pair of complementary divisors of the positive integer numbers x both lie in the 1st or both lie in the 4th quadrant. The pair of complementary divisors of the negative integer numbers x has one of the divisors in the 2nd quadrant and another divisor in the 3rd quadrant.

Thus, there is no trivial symmetry between the divisors of positive numbers and the divisors of negative numbers.

The divisors of positive numbers correspond within the same quadrant (1st or 4th), since both are present in the same quadrant.

The divisors of negative numbers correspond in different quadrants (2nd and 3rd), because each divisor must have the opposite sign of the other.

5.1 The pairs of complementary divisors for positive integers

From Figure 22, we use a linear way to join the pairs of divisors of the integers. For $x > 0$, we use a pair of infinite rays that start of each point representing a square on the C-parabola. Inside the C-parabola the rays are parallel and functional like a beam of light coming from the infinite. Outside the C-parabola the rays are diagonals with all the slopes $1/y$, where y is the Y-coordinate of the point representing the square on the C-parabola where the ray begins.

For positive integers in Q1, we multiply each consecutive value of d_2 by the value of its slope $d_1 = y$. Only in this way does the value of the X-axis coordinate take the value $x = d_1 * d_2$.

For positive integers in Q1, the horizontal ray in the form of $y = n$ cover the divisors $d_1 = y \leq \sqrt{|x|}$ from sequence <https://oeis.org/A161906> or <https://oeis.org/A319135>. They are inside the C-parabola. At each horizontal ray, the divisors d_1 have the same value n given by the Y-axis coordinate $y = n$.

For positive integers in Q1, the diagonal lines in the form of $x = ny$ (or $y = \frac{x}{n}$) cover the divisors $d_2 = y \geq \sqrt{|x|}$ from sequences <https://oeis.org/A340791> or <https://oeis.org/A161908>. They are outside the parabola. At each diagonal ray, the divisors $d_2 = y = \frac{x}{n} = \frac{x}{d_1}$ take on the consecutive value $n = d_1$ given by the y coordinate $y = n = d_1$.

Only the central pair of complementary divisors of the positive square numbers of the X-axis has two divisors with the same absolute value. They are the divisors $d_1 = d_2 = y = \pm\sqrt{|x|}$. From these divisors will start all pairs of horizontal and diagonal rays.

For positive integers, the two divisors ($d_1; d_2$) of the pairs of complementary divisors belong to Q1 or both to Q4. One divisor must be on a horizontal ray and the other on the corresponding diagonal ray. Since the two divisors must have the same sign, all the horizontal and diagonal rays' pairs are always in the same quadrant Q1 or Q4.

5.2 The pairs of complementary divisors for negative integers

Here on the negative side, we use a single finite segment connecting one divisor in Q2 and the other in Q3. All segments are vertical.

For negative integer numbers, each divisor of the pair of complementary divisors must have a different sign. Then, each divisor in the pair of complementary divisors must be in different quadrants. One divisor must be in Q2 and the other in Q3. Therefore, all the segments connecting the complementary divisors are vertical.

We will show ahead two more elaborate ways that show the perfect relationship between the divisors of pairs of complementary divisors. One form is parabolic (C002820 The Parabolic Framework of MID), and the other is hyperbolic (C002821 The Hyperbolic Framework of MID).

5.3 Primes and composites defined by the complementary divisors

Because the number of divisors of each integer varies, then we list them in the form of arrays.

If d_1 is the array <https://oeis.org/A161906> then, d_2 must be <https://oeis.org/A340791>.

If d_1 is the array <https://oeis.org/A319135> then, d_2 must be <https://oeis.org/A161908>.

Also, there is a bijection between the central pair of complementary divisors, and the trivial pair of complementary divisors with all integers.

We denominate any trivial pair of complementary divisors of an integer x as (d_{t1}, d_{t2}) , for $d_{t2} \geq d_{t1}$ and $x = d_{t1} * d_{t2}$.

We denominate any central pair of complementary divisors of an integer x as (d_{c1}, d_{c2}) , for $d_{c2} \geq d_{c1}$ and $x = d_{c1} * d_{c2}$. The sequences for positive d_{c1} and d_{c2} are:

- The sequence for positive d_{c1} is <https://oeis.org/A033676>.
- The sequence for positive d_{c2} is <https://oeis.org/A033677>.

Every positive or negative prime number (including ± 1) has the central pair of complementary divisors equal to the trivial pair of complementary divisors.

Every positive or negative composite number (including 0) has a central pair of complementary divisors different from the trivial pair of complementary divisors.

5.4 The number of complementary divisors

The **number of positive divisors** of a positive integer number $x > 0$ is a finite number $d[x]$ from the sequence <https://oeis.org/A000005>.

Considering every divisor of a positive integer number $x > 0$ belong to a **pair of complementary divisors** $(d_1; d_2)$ such as $x = d_1 d_2$, then the square numbers also must have an even number of divisors.

So, the **number of complementary divisors** of a positive integer number $x > 0$ is $d_d[x]$ the sequence <https://oeis.org/A161841> = <https://oeis.org/A000005> + <https://oeis.org/A010052>.

5.5 The sum and the difference between the complementary divisors

Because the use of complementary divisors to define primes and composites, it is important to analyze the difference (and the sum for negatives) between the two divisors that make up the pair of complementary divisors of integers.

We express the **sum of the two complementary divisors** d_1 and d_2 of an integer $x = d_1 d_2 > 0$, as $b_s = d_2 + d_1$, and the **difference of the two complementary divisors** as $b_d = d_2 - d_1 \geq 0$.

The number of sums of the 2 divisors of the distinct pairs of complementary divisors $\#b_s[x]$ is always equal to the number of differences $\#b_d[x]$.

The number of sums or differences of distinct pairs of complementary divisors of a positive integer $x > 0$ is $\#b_s[x] = \#b_d[x] = \text{https://oeis.org/A038548} = (\text{https://oeis.org/A161841} / 2)$.

6 The difference between the two complementary divisors

We define b_d as the difference between the two divisors of any pair of complementary divisors of an integer $x = d_1 * d_2$ such that:

$$b_d = d_2 - d_1 \geq 0$$

Because we require always $d_2 \geq d_1$, then b_d is always positive.

Because $x = d_1 * d_2$, then $x = d_2 * d_1$. We refer to these two forms as the hyperbolic form.

From each of the two hyperbolic forms, it is possible to find two parabolic forms using b_d :

$$\begin{aligned} x &= d_1(d_1 + b_d) = d_1^2 + b_d d_1 \\ x &= d_2(d_2 - b_d) = d_2^2 - b_d d_2 \end{aligned}$$

6.1 Behavior of the differences between pair of divisors of positive integers

We usually say that the integer 24 has 8 divisors. This is because we usually only consider the positive divisors.

But MID shows us that we must also consider the negative divisors.

For example, the 16 points on the vertical $x = 24$ of MID tells us that there are 16 divisors for the integer +24.

The integer 24 in the MID has eight positive divisors $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 12, 24\}$ and eight negative divisors $\{-24, -12, -8, -6, -4, -3, -2, -1\}$.

Considering the set of its 8 positive divisors in ascending order to be $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 12, 24\}$ distributed along the Q1 quadrant for the positive integer +24, there are 4 distinct values of differences between the divisors in the pairs of complementary divisors:

$d_1 \leq \sqrt{24}$	$d_2 \geq \sqrt{24}$	Hyperbolic $x = d_1 * d_2$	Hyperbolic $x = d_2 * d_1$	$b_d = d_2 - d_1$	Parabolic $d_1 (d_1 + b_d)$	Parabolic $d_2 (d_2 - b_d)$
1	24	1 * 24	24 * 1	23	1(1 + 23)	24(24 - 23)
2	12	2 * 12	12 * 2	10	2(2 + 10)	12(12 - 10)
3	8	3 * 8	8 * 3	5	3(3 + 5)	8(8 - 5)
4	6	4 * 6	6 * 4	2	4(4 + 2)	6(6 - 2)

Figure 23. The difference between the divisors of the complementary pairs of 24 in Q1.

Considering the set of its 8 negative divisors in ascending order to be $\{-24, -12, -8, -6, -4, -3, -2, -1\}$ distributed along the Q4 quadrant for the positive integer +24, there are also 4 distinct values of differences between the divisors in the pairs of complementary divisors:

$d_1 \leq - \sqrt{24} $	$d_2 \geq - \sqrt{24} $	Hyperbolic $x = d_1 * d_2$	Hyperbolic $x = d_2 * d_1$	$b_d = d_2 - d_1$	Parabolic $d_1 (d_1 + b_d)$	Parabolic $d_2 (d_2 - b_d)$
-24	-1	-24 * -1	-1 * -24	23	-24(-24 + 23)	-1(-1 - 23)
-12	-2	-12 * -2	-2 * -12	10	-12(-12 + 10)	-2(-2 - 10)
-8	-3	-8 * -3	-3 * -8	5	-8(-8 + 5)	-3(-3 - 5)
-6	-4	-6 * -4	-4 * -6	2	-6(-6 + 2)	-4(-4 - 2)

Figure 24. The difference between the divisors of the complementary pairs of 24 in Q4.

Note we always respect $d_2 \geq d_1$.

6.2 Behavior of the differences between pair of divisors of negative integers

See what happens when we evaluate the pairs of divisors of a negative integer. Half of its divisors will be positive, and the other half will be negative divisors.

For example, integer -24 has 4 negative divisors and 4 positive divisors.

In the MID, integer -24 has 8 divisors in ascending order to be $\{-4, -3, -2, -1, 6, 8, 12, 24\}$ and more 8 divisors in ascending order to be $\{-24, -12, -8, -6, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$. MID shows all the 16 divisors of the integer -24.

Both integers +24 and -24 have the same 16 divisors. The different usage is because of the combination when the complementary pairs match differently.

Considering the set of its divisors in ascending order being $\{-4, -3, -2, -1, 6, 8, 12, 24\}$ distributed along the Q3 and Q2 quadrants for the negative integer -24, there are 4 distinct values of differences between the divisors in the pairs of complementary divisors:

$d_1 \geq - \sqrt{24} $	$d_2 \geq \sqrt{24} $	Hyperbolic $x = d_1 * d_2$	Hyperbolic $x = d_2 * d_1$	$b_d = d_2 - d_1$	Parabolic $d_1 (d_1 + b_d)$	Parabolic $d_2 (d_2 - b_d)$
-4	6	-4 * 6	6 * -4	10	-4(-4 + 10)	6(6 - 10)
-3	8	-3 * 8	8 * -3	11	-3(-3 + 11)	8(8 - 11)
-2	12	-2 * 12	12 * -2	14	-2(-2 + 14)	12(12 - 14)
-1	24	-1 * 24	24 * -1	25	-1(-1 + 25)	24(24 - 25)

Figure 25. The difference between the divisors of the complementary pairs of -24 for d_1 in Q3, d_2 in Q2, and $d_1 \geq -|\sqrt{24}|$.

Considering the set of its divisors in ascending order to be $\{-24, -12, -8, -6, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ also distributed along the Q3 and Q2 quadrants for the negative integer -24, there are 4 distinct values of differences between the divisors in the pairs of complementary divisors:

$d_1 \leq - \sqrt{24} $	$d_2 \leq \sqrt{24} $	Hyperbolic $x = d_1 * d_2$	Hyperbolic $x = d_2 * d_1$	$b_d = d_2 - d_1$	Parabolic $d_1 (d_1 + b_d)$	Parabolic $d_2 (d_2 - b_d)$
-24	1	-24*1	1 * -24	25	-24(-24 + 25)	1(1 - 25)
-12	2	-12 * 2	2 * -12	14	-12(-12 + 14)	2(2 - 14)
-8	3	-8 * 3	3 * -8	11	-8(-8 + 11)	3(3 - 11)
-6	4	-6 * 4	4 * -6	10	-6(-6 + 10)	4(4 - 10)

Figure 26. The difference between the divisors of the complementary pairs of -24 for d_1 in Q3, d_2 in Q2, and $d_1 \leq -|\sqrt{24}|$.

7 The sum of the two complementary divisors

Let us define b_s as the sum of the two divisors of any pair of complementary divisors of an integer $x = d_1 * d_2$, where $d_2 > d_1$ such that:

$$b_s = d_2 + d_1$$

Because of this definition, and because one or both divisors can be negative, then b_s may be positive or negative.

Because $x = d_1 * d_2$, then $x = d_2 * d_1$. We refer to these two forms as the hyperbolic form.

From each of the two hyperbolic forms, it is possible to find two parabolic forms:

$$\begin{aligned} x &= d_1(-d_1 + b_s) = -d_1(d_1 - b_s) = -d_1^2 + b_s d_1 \\ x &= d_2(-d_2 + b_s) = -d_2(d_2 - b_s) = -d_2^2 + b_s d_2 \end{aligned}$$

7.1 Behavior of the sums on positive integers

Considering the set of its 8 positive divisors in ascending order to be $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 12, 24\}$ distributed along the Q1 quadrant for the positive integer $+24$, there are 4 distinct values of the sums of the divisors in the pairs of complementary divisors:

$d_1 \leq \sqrt{24} $	$d_2 \geq \sqrt{24} $	Hyperbolic $x = d_1 * d_2$	Hyperbolic $x = d_2 * d_1$	$b_s = d_2 + d_1$	Parabolic $-d_1(d_1 - b_s)$	Parabolic $-d_2(d_2 - b_s)$
1	24	1 * 24	24 * 1	25	-1(1 - 25)	-24(24 - 25)
2	12	2 * 12	12 * 2	14	-2(2 - 14)	-12(12 - 14)
3	8	3 * 8	8 * 3	11	-3(3 - 11)	-8(8 - 11)
4	6	4 * 6	6 * 4	10	-4(4 - 10)	-6(6 - 10)

Figure 27. The sum of the divisors of the complementary pairs of 24 in Q1.

Considering the set of its 8 negative divisors in ascending order to be $\{-24, -12, -8, -6, -4, -3, -2, -1\}$ distributed along the Q4 quadrant for the positive integer $+24$, there are also 4 distinct values of the sums of the divisors in the pairs of complementary divisors:

$d_1 \leq - \sqrt{24} $	$d_2 \geq - \sqrt{24} $	Hyperbolic $x = d_1 * d_2$	Hyperbolic $x = d_2 * d_1$	$b_s = d_2 + d_1$	Parabolic $-d_1(d_1 - b_s)$	Parabolic $-d_2(d_2 - b_s)$
-24	-1	-24 * -1	-1 * -24	-25	24(-24 + 25)	1(-1 + 25)
-12	-2	-12 * -2	-2 * -12	-14	12(-12 + 14)	2(-2 + 14)
-8	-3	-8 * -3	-3 * -8	-11	8(-8 + 11)	3(-3 + 11)
-6	-4	-6 * -4	-4 * -6	-10	6(-6 + 10)	4(-4 + 10)

Figure 28. The sum of the divisors of the complementary pairs of 24 in Q4.

7.2 Behavior of the sums on negative integers

Considering the set of its divisors in ascending order to be $\{-4, -3, -2, -1, 6, 8, 12, 24\}$ distributed along the Q3 and Q2 quadrants for the negative integer -24 , there are 4 distinct values of the sums of the divisors in the pairs of complementary divisors:

$d_1 \geq - \sqrt{24} $	$d_2 \geq \sqrt{24} $	Hyperbolic $x = d_1 * d_2$	Hyperbolic $x = d_2 * d_1$	$b_s = d_2 + d_1$	Parabolic $-d_1 (d_1 - b_s)$	Parabolic $-d_2 (d_2 - b_s)$
-4	6	$-4 * 6$	$6 * -4$	2	$4(-4 - 2)$	$-6(6 - 2)$
-3	8	$-3 * 8$	$8 * -3$	5	$3(-3 - 5)$	$-8(8 - 5)$
-2	12	$-2 * 12$	$12 * -2$	10	$2(-2 - 10)$	$-12(12 - 10)$
-1	24	$-1 * 24$	$24 * -1$	23	$1(-1 - 23)$	$-24(24 - 23)$

Figure 29. The sums of the divisors of the complementary pairs of -24 for d_1 in Q3, d_2 in Q2, and $d_1 \geq -|\sqrt{24}|$.

Considering the set of its divisors in ascending order to be $\{-24, -12, -8, -6, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ also distributed along the Q3 and Q2 quadrants for the negative integer -24 , there are 4 distinct values of the sums of the divisors in the pairs of complementary divisors:

$d_1 \leq - \sqrt{24} $	$d_2 \leq \sqrt{24} $	Hyperbolic $x = d_1 * d_2$	Hyperbolic $x = d_2 * d_1$	$b_s = d_2 + d_1$	Parabolic $-d_1 (d_1 - b_s)$	Parabolic $-d_2 (d_2 - b_s)$
-24	1	$-24 * 1$	$1 * -24$	-23	$24(-24 + 23)$	$-1(1 + 23)$
-12	2	$-12 * 2$	$2 * -12$	-10	$12(-12 + 10)$	$-2(2 + 10)$
-8	3	$-8 * 3$	$3 * -8$	-5	$8(-8 + 5)$	$-3(3 + 5)$
-6	4	$-6 * 4$	$4 * -6$	-2	$6(-6 + 2)$	$-4(4 + 2)$

Figure 30. The sums of the divisors of the complementary pairs of -24 for d_1 in Q3, d_2 in Q2, and $d_1 \leq -|\sqrt{24}|$.

8 C000725 The trivial pair of complementary divisors

We will name every trivial pair of complementary divisors as $(d_{t1}; d_{t2})$, and $d_{t2} \geq d_{t1}$.

Because of this definition, always d_{t1} of the negative integers will be in Q3 of MID and d_{t2} will be in Q2. For positive integers, d_{t1} and d_{t2} will be in Q1 or both in Q4.

Based on the MID, any positive or negative prime or composite number has two trivial pairs of complementary divisors. Number 1 or -1 has only one trivial pair of complementary divisors. Because the number 0 is undefined, but it is a square number, we will define its trivial pair of complementary divisors as $(0; 0)$.

So, for integers $|x| = |d_{t1} * d_{t2}| = 1$, we have two trivial pairs of complementary divisors: $(-1; 1)$ and $(1; 1)$.

For integers $|x| = |d_{t1} * d_{t2}| > 1$, we have four trivial pairs of complementary divisors: $(-|x|; 1)$, $(-1; |x|)$, $(1; |x|)$, and $(-|x|; -1)$.

Because of our definition, for $x = 0$, we have one trivial pair of complementary divisors: $(0; 0)$.

Now, let us see how the trivial pairs of complementary divisors behave in the MID.

Considering only the increasing direction of the X-axis, then there are 4 possibilities to see the trivial divisors of all integers in the MID, one for each quadrant.

See below the location of the divisor's points on the MID. In all cases, we use d_{t_1} in magenta color, and d_{t_2} in violet.

8.1 $d_{t_1} \leq -\lfloor\sqrt{|x|}\rfloor$ in Q3, $d_{t_1} \leq \lfloor\sqrt{x}\rfloor$ in Q1, and $d_{t_2} \geq d_{t_1}$ in Q2_Q1

Product I: $integers = x = \sqrt{-A000027} * A000012$

	Q3		Q2
	Q1		Q1
	$\sqrt{-A000027}$		A000012
A256958	A000012	A256958	A000027
$x = d_{t_1} * d_{t_2}$	$y = d_{t_1}$	$x = d_{t_1} * d_{t_2}$	
-25	-25	-25	1
-24	-24	-24	1
-23	-23	-23	1
-22	-22	-22	1
-21	-21	-21	1
-20	-20	-20	1
-19	-19	-19	1
-18	-18	-18	1
-17	-17	-17	1
-16	-16	-16	1
-15	-15	-15	1
-14	-14	-14	1
-13	-13	-13	1
-12	-12	-12	1
-11	-11	-11	1
-10	-10	-10	1
-9	-9	-9	1
-8	-8	-8	1
-7	-7	-7	1
-6	-6	-6	1
-5	-5	-5	1
-4	-4	-4	1
-3	-3	-3	1
-2	-2	-2	1
-1	-1	-1	1
0	0	0	0
1	1	1	1
2	1	2	2
3	1	3	3
4	1	4	4
5	1	5	5
6	1	6	6
7	1	7	7
8	1	8	8
9	1	9	9
10	1	10	10
11	1	11	11
12	1	12	12
13	1	13	13
14	1	14	14
15	1	15	15
16	1	16	16
17	1	17	17
18	1	18	18
19	1	19	19
20	1	20	20
21	1	21	21
22	1	22	22
23	1	23	23
24	1	24	24
25	1	25	25

Figure 31. [C000725](#) Table of coordinates of trivial divisors for $d_{t_1} \leq -\lfloor\sqrt{|x|}\rfloor$ in Q3, $d_{t_1} \leq \lfloor\sqrt{x}\rfloor$ in Q1, and $d_{t_2} \geq d_{t_1}$ in Q2 and in Q1.

For the negative numbers $x < 0$, d_{t1} starts as $\setminus\text{A000027}\setminus$ in Q3, passes through zero, and continues in the positive numbers $x > 0$ as A000012 in Q1. We will name this sequence as $\setminus\text{A000027}\&0\&\text{A000012} = \{\dots, -25, -24, -23, -22, -21, -20, -19, -18, -17, -16, -15, -14, -13, -12, -11, -10, -9, -8, -7, -6, -5, -4, -3, -2, -1, 0, 1, \dots\}$.

For the negative numbers $x < 0$, d_{t2} starts as A000012 in Q2, passes through zero, and continues in the positive numbers $x > 0$ as A000027 in Q1. We will name this sequence as $\text{A000012}\&0\&\text{A000027} = \{\dots, 1, 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, \dots\}$.

Figure 32. C000725 MID display of trivial divisors for $d_{t1} \leq -\sqrt{|x|}$ in Q3, $d_{t1} \leq \sqrt{x}$ in Q1, and $d_{t2} \geq d_{t1}$ in Q2 and in Q1.

8.2 $d_{t1} \geq -\left|\sqrt{|x|}\right|$ in Q3, $d_{t1} \leq \left|\sqrt{x}\right|$ in Q1, and $d_{t2} \geq d_{t1}$ in Q2_Q1

Product II: *integers* = \-A000012&0&A000012 * \A000027&0&A000027

	Q3		Q2
	Q1		Q1
	-A000012		\A000027\
A256958	A000012	A256958	A000027
$x = d_{t1} * d_{t2}$	$y = d_{t1}$	$x = d_{t1} * d_{t2}$	$y = d_{t2}$
-25	-1	-25	25
-24	-1	-24	24
-23	-1	-23	23
-22	-1	-22	22
-21	-1	-21	21
-20	-1	-20	20
-19	-1	-19	19
-18	-1	-18	18
-17	-1	-17	17
-16	-1	-16	16
-15	-1	-15	15
-14	-1	-14	14
-13	-1	-13	13
-12	-1	-12	12
-11	-1	-11	11
-10	-1	-10	10
-9	-1	-9	9
-8	-1	-8	8
-7	-1	-7	7
-6	-1	-6	6
-5	-1	-5	5
-4	-1	-4	4
-3	-1	-3	3
-2	-1	-2	2
-1	-1	-1	1
0	0	0	0
1	1	1	1
2	1	2	2
3	1	3	3
4	1	4	4
5	1	5	5
6	1	6	6
7	1	7	7
8	1	8	8
9	1	9	9
10	1	10	10
11	1	11	11
12	1	12	12
13	1	13	13
14	1	14	14
15	1	15	15
16	1	16	16
17	1	17	17
18	1	18	18
19	1	19	19
20	1	20	20
21	1	21	21
22	1	22	22
23	1	23	23
24	1	24	24
25	1	25	25

Figure 33. [C000725](#) Table of coordinates of trivial divisors for $d_{t1} \geq -\left|\sqrt{|x|}\right|$ in Q3, $d_{t1} \leq \left|\sqrt{x}\right|$ in Q1, and $d_{t2} \geq d_{t1}$ in Q2 and in Q1.

For the negative numbers $x < 0$, d_{t1} starts as $-\text{A000012}$ in Q3, passes through zero, and continues in the positive numbers $x > 0$ as A000012 in Q1. We will name this sequence as $-\text{A000012} \& \text{A000012} = \{\dots, -1, 0, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, \dots\}$.

For the negative numbers $x < 0$, d_{t2} starts as A000027 in Q2, passes through zero, and continues in the positive numbers $x > 0$ as A000027 in Q1. We will name this sequence as $\text{A000027} \& \text{A000027} = \{\dots, 25, 24, 23, 22, 21, 20, 19, 18, 17, 16, 15, 14, 13, 12, 11, 10, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, \dots\}$.

Figure 34. C000725 MID display of trivial divisors for $d_{t1} \geq -\sqrt{|x|}$ in Q3, $d_{t1} \leq \sqrt{x}$ in Q1, and $d_{t2} \geq d_{t1}$ in Q2 and in Q1.

8.3 $d_{t1} \leq -\left\lfloor \sqrt{|x|} \right\rfloor$ in Q3, $d_{t1} \leq -\left\lfloor \sqrt{x} \right\rfloor$ in Q4, and $d_{t2} \geq d_{t1}$ in Q2_Q4

Product III: $integers = \setminus -A000027 \setminus \&0\& - A000027 * A000012 \&0\& - A000012$

Q3		Q2	
Q4		Q4	
\setminus -A000027 \setminus		A000012	
A256958	-A000027	A256958	-A000012
$x = d_{t1} * d_{t2}$	$y = d_{t1}$	$x = d_{t1} * d_{t2}$	$y = d_{t2}$
-25	-25	-25	1
-24	-24	-24	1
-23	-23	-23	1
-22	-22	-22	1
-21	-21	-21	1
-20	-20	-20	1
-19	-19	-19	1
-18	-18	-18	1
-17	-17	-17	1
-16	-16	-16	1
-15	-15	-15	1
-14	-14	-14	1
-13	-13	-13	1
-12	-12	-12	1
-11	-11	-11	1
-10	-10	-10	1
-9	-9	-9	1
-8	-8	-8	1
-7	-7	-7	1
-6	-6	-6	1
-5	-5	-5	1
-4	-4	-4	1
-3	-3	-3	1
-2	-2	-2	1
-1	-1	-1	1
0	0	0	0
1	-1	1	-1
2	-2	2	-1
3	-3	3	-1
4	-4	4	-1
5	-5	5	-1
6	-6	6	-1
7	-7	7	-1
8	-8	8	-1
9	-9	9	-1
10	-10	10	-1
11	-11	11	-1
12	-12	12	-1
13	-13	13	-1
14	-14	14	-1
15	-15	15	-1
16	-16	16	-1
17	-17	17	-1
18	-18	18	-1
19	-19	19	-1
20	-20	20	-1
21	-21	21	-1
22	-22	22	-1
23	-23	23	-1
24	-24	24	-1
25	-25	25	-1

Figure 35. [C000725](#) Table of coordinates of trivial divisors for $d_{t1} \leq -\left\lfloor \sqrt{|x|} \right\rfloor$ in Q3, $d_{t1} \leq \left\lfloor \sqrt{x} \right\rfloor$ in Q1, and $d_{t2} \geq d_{t1}$ in Q2 and in Q4.

For the negative numbers $x < 0$, d_{t1} starts as $\setminus\text{A000027}\setminus$ in Q3, passes through zero, and continues in the positive numbers $x > 0$ as A000027 in Q4. We will name this sequence as $\setminus\text{A000027}\&0\&\text{A000027} = \{\dots, -25, -24, -23, -22, -21, -20, -19, -18, -17, -16, -15, -14, -13, -12, -11, -10, -9, -8, -7, -6, -5, -4, -3, -2, -1, 0, -1, -2, -3, -4, -5, -6, -7, -8, -9, -10, -11, -12, -13, -14, -15, -16, -17, -18, -19, -20, -21, -22, -23, -24, -25, \dots\}$.

For the negative numbers $x < 0$, d_{t2} starts as A000012 in Q2, passes through zero, and continues in the positive numbers $x > 0$ as $\setminus\text{A000012}\setminus$ in Q4. We will name this sequence as $\text{A000012}\&0\&\setminus\text{A000012}\setminus = \{\dots, 1, 0, -1, \dots\}$.

Figure 36. C000725 MID display of trivial divisors for $d_{t1} \leq -\sqrt{|x|}$ in Q3, $d_{t1} \leq \sqrt{x}$ in Q1, and $d_{t2} \geq d_{t1}$ in Q2 and in Q1.

8.4 $d_{t1} \geq -|\sqrt{|x|}|$ in Q3, $d_{t1} \leq -|\sqrt{x}|$ in Q4, and $d_{t2} \geq d_{t1}$ in Q2_Q4

Product IV: *integers* = -A000012&0&- A000027 * \A000027&0&- A000012

		Q3			Q2
		Q4			Q4
		-A000012			\A000027\
A256958	-A000027	A256958	-A000012	A256958	-A000012
$x = d_{t1} * d_{t2}$	$y = d_{t1}$	$x = d_{t1} * d_{t2}$	$y = d_{t1}$	$x = d_{t1} * d_{t2}$	$y = d_{t2}$
-25	-1	-25	-1	-25	25
-24	-1	-24	-1	-24	24
-23	-1	-23	-1	-23	23
-22	-1	-22	-1	-22	22
-21	-1	-21	-1	-21	21
-20	-1	-20	-1	-20	20
-19	-1	-19	-1	-19	19
-18	-1	-18	-1	-18	18
-17	-1	-17	-1	-17	17
-16	-1	-16	-1	-16	16
-15	-1	-15	-1	-15	15
-14	-1	-14	-1	-14	14
-13	-1	-13	-1	-13	13
-12	-1	-12	-1	-12	12
-11	-1	-11	-1	-11	11
-10	-1	-10	-1	-10	10
-9	-1	-9	-1	-9	9
-8	-1	-8	-1	-8	8
-7	-1	-7	-1	-7	7
-6	-1	-6	-1	-6	6
-5	-1	-5	-1	-5	5
-4	-1	-4	-1	-4	4
-3	-1	-3	-1	-3	3
-2	-1	-2	-1	-2	2
-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	1
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	-1	1	-1	1	-1
2	-1	2	-1	2	-1
3	-1	3	-1	3	-1
4	-1	4	-1	4	-1
5	-1	5	-1	5	-1
6	-1	6	-1	6	-1
7	-1	7	-1	7	-1
8	-1	8	-1	8	-1
9	-1	9	-1	9	-1
10	-1	10	-1	10	-1
11	-1	11	-1	11	-1
12	-1	12	-1	12	-1
13	-1	13	-1	13	-1
14	-1	14	-1	14	-1
15	-1	15	-1	15	-1
16	-1	16	-1	16	-1
17	-1	17	-1	17	-1
18	-1	18	-1	18	-1
19	-1	19	-1	19	-1
20	-1	20	-1	20	-1
21	-1	21	-1	21	-1
22	-1	22	-1	22	-1
23	-1	23	-1	23	-1
24	-1	24	-1	24	-1
25	-1	25	-1	25	-1

Figure 37. [C000725](#) Table of coordinates of trivial divisors for $d_{t1} \geq -|\sqrt{|x|}|$ in Q3, $d_{t1} \leq -|\sqrt{x}|$ in Q1, and $d_{t2} \geq d_{t1}$ in Q2 and in Q4.

9 C000721 The largest difference between all complementary divisors

Let us define b_{dM} as the largest (maximum absolute value) difference between all pairs of complementary divisors of an integer $x = d_{t1} * d_{t2} = 1 * x$ such that:

$$b_{dM} = \text{largest } d_2 - \text{smallest } d_1$$

In this way, always b_{dM} is

$$b_{dM} = d_{t2} - d_{t1} \geq 0$$

Because of this definition, we require always $d_{t2} \geq d_{t1}$. To comply with the largest difference:

- d_{t1} is the smallest trivial complementary divisor. It may be +1, -1, or $-|x|$. It will never be $|x|$. $d_{t1} \neq |x|$.
- d_{t2} is the largest trivial complementary divisor. It may be +1, -1, or $+|x|$. It will never be $-|x|$. $d_{t2} \neq -|x|$.

Because $x = d_{t1} * d_{t2}$, then $x = d_{t2} * d_{t1}$. We call these two forms the hyperbolic form.

From each of the two hyperbolic forms, it is possible to find two parabolic forms:

$$x = d_{t1}(d_{t1} + b_{dM}) = d_{t1}^2 + b_{dM}d_{t1}$$

$$x = d_{t2}(d_{t2} - b_{dM}) = d_{t2}^2 - b_{dM}d_{t2}$$

9.1 Example: the largest difference for integers +24 and -24

Considering the set of its 8 positive divisors in ascending order to be {1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 12, 24} distributed along the Q1 quadrant for the positive integer +24, there are 4 distinct values of differences between the divisors in the pairs of complementary divisors. Consequently, there is one value of the largest difference between the divisors in the pairs of complementary positive divisors of the number +24:

$d_{t1} \leq \sqrt{24} $	$d_{t2} \geq \sqrt{24} $	Hyperbolic $x = d_{t1} * d_{t2}$	Hyperbolic $x = d_{t2} * d_{t1}$	$b_{dM} = d_{t2} - d_{t1}$	Parabolic $d_{t1} (d_{t1} + b_{dM})$	Parabolic $d_{t2} (d_{t2} - b_{dM})$
1	24	1 * 24	24 * 1	23	1(1 + 23)	24(24 - 23)

Figure 39. The largest difference of all pairs of complementary divisors from {1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 12, 24} for 24.

Considering the set of its 8 negative divisors in ascending order to be {-24, -12, -8, -6, -4, -3, -2, -1} distributed along the Q4 quadrant for the positive integer +24, there are also 4 distinct values of differences between the divisors in the pairs of complementary divisors. Consequently, there is one value of the largest difference between the divisors in the pairs of complementary negative divisors for the number +24:

$d_{t1} \leq - \sqrt{24} $	$d_{t2} \geq - \sqrt{24} $	Hyperbolic $x = d_{t1} * d_{t2}$	Hyperbolic $x = d_{t2} * d_{t1}$	$b_{dM} = d_{t2} - d_{t1}$	Parabolic $d_{t1} (d_{t1} + b_{dM})$	Parabolic $d_{t2} (d_{t2} - b_{dM})$
-24	-1	-24 * -1	-1 * -24	23	-24(-24 + 23)	-1(-1 - 23)

Figure 40. The largest difference of all pairs of complementary divisors from {-24, -12, -8, -6, -4, -3, -2, -1} for 24.

Both cases have the same result. So, we consider 23 as being the largest difference of all pairs of complementary divisors of 24.

Considering the set of its divisors in ascending order to be $\{-4, -3, -2, -1, 6, 8, 12, 24\}$ distributed along the Q3 and Q2 quadrants for the negative integer -24 , there are 4 distinct values of differences between the divisors in the pairs of complementary divisors. Consequently, there is one value of the largest difference between the divisors in the pairs of complementary negative and positive divisors for the number -24 :

$d_{t1} \geq - \sqrt{24} $	$d_{t2} \geq \sqrt{24} $	Hyperbolic $x = d_{t1} * d_{t2}$	Hyperbolic $x = d_{t2} * d_{t1}$	$b_{dM} = d_{t2} - d_{t1}$	Parabolic $d_{t1} (d_{t1} + b_{dM})$	Parabolic $d_{t2} (d_{t2} - b_{dM})$
-1	24	-1 * 24	24 * -1	25	-1(-1 + 25)	24(24 - 25)

Figure 41. The largest difference of all pairs of complementary divisors from $\{-4, -3, -2, -1, 6, 8, 12, 24\}$ for -24 .

Considering the set of its divisors in ascending order to be $\{-24, -12, -8, -6, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ distributed along the Q3 and Q2 quadrants for the negative integer -24 , there are 4 distinct values of differences between the divisors in the pairs of complementary divisors. Consequently, there is one value of the largest difference between the divisors in the pairs of complementary negative and positive divisors for the number -24 :

$d_{t1} \leq - \sqrt{24} $	$d_{t2} \leq \sqrt{24} $	Hyperbolic $x = d_{t1} * d_{t2}$	Hyperbolic $x = d_{t2} * d_{t1}$	$b_{dM} = d_{t2} - d_{t1}$	Parabolic $d_{t1} (d_{t1} + b_{dM})$	Parabolic $d_{t2} (d_{t2} - b_{dM})$
-24	1	-24*1	1 * -24	25	-24(-24 + 25)	1(1 - 25)

Figure 42. The largest difference of all pairs of complementary divisors from $\{-24, -12, -8, -6, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ for -24 .

Both cases have the same result. So, we consider 25 as being the largest difference of all pairs of complementary divisors of -24 .

9.2 The sequence [C000721](#)

We must analyze 4 cases to get the sequence of the largest difference of the pairs of complementary divisors of the integers.

	Q3	Q2	-	Q3	Q2	-	Q3	Q2	-	Q3	Q2	-
	Q1	Q1	C00072 1	Q1	Q1	C00072 1	Q4	Q4	C00072 1	Q4	Q4	C00072 1
	$\sqrt{-}$ A00002 7\	A0000 12	$\sqrt{A0207}$ 25\	A0000 12	$\sqrt{A00002}$ 7\	$\sqrt{A0207}$ 25\	$\sqrt{-}$ A00002 7\	A0000 12	$\sqrt{A0207}$ 25\	A0000 12	$\sqrt{A00002}$ 7\	$\sqrt{A0207}$ 25\
A2569 58	A00001 2	A0000 27	A00147 7	A0000 12	A000027	A00147 7	- A00002 7	- A0000 12	A00147 7	- A0000 27	- A000012	A00147 7
$x = d_{t1} * d_{t2}$	d_{t1}	d_{t2}	$b_{dM} = d_{t2} - d_{t1}$	d_{t1}	d_{t2}	$b_{dM} = d_{t2} - d_{t1}$	d_{t1}	d_{t2}	$b_{dM} = d_{t2} - d_{t1}$	d_{t1}	d_{t2}	$b_{dM} = d_{t2} - d_{t1}$
-25	-25	1	26	-1	25	26	-25	1	26	-1	25	26
-24	-24	1	25	-1	24	25	-24	1	25	-1	24	25
-23	-23	1	24	-1	23	24	-23	1	24	-1	23	24
-22	-22	1	23	-1	22	23	-22	1	23	-1	22	23
-21	-21	1	22	-1	21	22	-21	1	22	-1	21	22
-20	-20	1	21	-1	20	21	-20	1	21	-1	20	21
-19	-19	1	20	-1	19	20	-19	1	20	-1	19	20
-18	-18	1	19	-1	18	19	-18	1	19	-1	18	19

-17	-17	1	18	-1	17	18	-17	1	18	-1	17	18
-16	-16	1	17	-1	16	17	-16	1	17	-1	16	17
-15	-15	1	16	-1	15	16	-15	1	16	-1	15	16
-14	-14	1	15	-1	14	15	-14	1	15	-1	14	15
-13	-13	1	14	-1	13	14	-13	1	14	-1	13	14
-12	-12	1	13	-1	12	13	-12	1	13	-1	12	13
-11	-11	1	12	-1	11	12	-11	1	12	-1	11	12
-10	-10	1	11	-1	10	11	-10	1	11	-1	10	11
-9	-9	1	10	-1	9	10	-9	1	10	-1	9	10
-8	-8	1	9	-1	8	9	-8	1	9	-1	8	9
-7	-7	1	8	-1	7	8	-7	1	8	-1	7	8
-6	-6	1	7	-1	6	7	-6	1	7	-1	6	7
-5	-5	1	6	-1	5	6	-5	1	6	-1	5	6
-4	-4	1	5	-1	4	5	-4	1	5	-1	4	5
-3	-3	1	4	-1	3	4	-3	1	4	-1	3	4
-2	-2	1	3	-1	2	3	-2	1	3	-1	2	3
-1	-1	1	2	-1	1	2	-1	1	2	-1	1	2
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	1	0	1	1	0	-1	-1	0	-1	-1	0
2	1	2	1	1	2	1	-2	-1	1	-2	-1	1
3	1	3	2	1	3	2	-3	-1	2	-3	-1	2
4	1	4	3	1	4	3	-4	-1	3	-4	-1	3
5	1	5	4	1	5	4	-5	-1	4	-5	-1	4
6	1	6	5	1	6	5	-6	-1	5	-6	-1	5
7	1	7	6	1	7	6	-7	-1	6	-7	-1	6
8	1	8	7	1	8	7	-8	-1	7	-8	-1	7
9	1	9	8	1	9	8	-9	-1	8	-9	-1	8
10	1	10	9	1	10	9	-10	-1	9	-10	-1	9
11	1	11	10	1	11	10	-11	-1	10	-11	-1	10
12	1	12	11	1	12	11	-12	-1	11	-12	-1	11
13	1	13	12	1	13	12	-13	-1	12	-13	-1	12
14	1	14	13	1	14	13	-14	-1	13	-14	-1	13
15	1	15	14	1	15	14	-15	-1	14	-15	-1	14
16	1	16	15	1	16	15	-16	-1	15	-16	-1	15
17	1	17	16	1	17	16	-17	-1	16	-17	-1	16
18	1	18	17	1	18	17	-18	-1	17	-18	-1	17
19	1	19	18	1	19	18	-19	-1	18	-19	-1	18
20	1	20	19	1	20	19	-20	-1	19	-20	-1	19
21	1	21	20	1	21	20	-21	-1	20	-21	-1	20
22	1	22	21	1	22	21	-22	-1	21	-22	-1	21
23	1	23	22	1	23	22	-23	-1	22	-23	-1	22
24	1	24	23	1	24	23	-24	-1	23	-24	-1	23
25	1	25	24	1	25	24	-25	-1	24	-25	-1	24

Figure 43. [C000721](#) Table of 4 possibilities to find the largest differences between the trivial pairs of complementary divisors of the integers $b_{dM} = d_{t2} - d_{t1}$.

There is only one solution for b_{dM} in all 4 cases.

The sequences for multiplier and multiplicand are <https://oeis.org/A000027> and <https://oeis.org/A000012>.

The sequences for the products are <https://oeis.org/A001477> and <https://oeis.org/A020725>.

The largest differences between the trivial pairs of complementary divisors of the integers is the sequence [C000721](#) = [\A020725](#) & [\A001477](#) = {..., 26, 25, 24, 23, 22, 21, 20, 19, 18, 17, 16, 15, 14, 13, 12, 11, 10, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 0, 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24,, ...}.

It has two zeros. One for integer 0 and other for the positive integer 1.

It is like the sequence in offset: [\A199969](#) & [\A000027](#).

See below the graph of this sequence in the XY plane.

Figure 44. [C000721](#) Graph of the largest differences between the trivial pairs of complementary divisors of the integers. The X-axis represents integer numbers, and the Y-axis represents the value of the largest differences.

10 C000723 The largest sum of all complementary divisors

Let us define b_{sM} as the largest (maximum value) sum of the two divisors of all pairs of complementary divisors of an integer $x = d_{t1} * d_{t2}$ such that:

$$b_{sM} = d_{t2} + d_{t1}$$

To comply with our divisor's definition, we require always $d_{t2} \geq d_{t1}$:

- d_{t1} is the smallest trivial complementary divisor. It may be +1, -1, or $-|x|$. It will never be $|x|$. $d_{t1} \neq |x|$.

- d_{t2} is the largest trivial complementary divisor. It may be $+1, -1, \text{ or } +|x|$. It will never be $-|x|$. $d_{t2} \neq -|x|$.

Because of this definition, and because one or both trivial divisors can be negative, then b_{sM} may be positive or negative.

Because $x = d_{t1} * d_{t2}$, then $x = d_{t2} * d_{t1}$. We refer to these two forms as the hyperbolic form.

From each of the two hyperbolic forms, it is possible to find two parabolic forms:

$$x = d_{t1}(-d_{t1} + b_{sM}) = -d_{t1}(d_{t1} - b_{sM}) = -d_{t1}^2 + b_{sM}d_{t1}$$

$$x = d_{t2}(-d_{t2} + b_{sM}) = -d_{t2}(d_{t2} - b_{sM}) = -d_{t2}^2 + b_{sM}d_{t2}$$

10.1 Example: the largest sum for integers +24 and -24

Considering the set of its 8 positive divisors in ascending order to be $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 12, 24\}$ distributed along the Q1 quadrant for the positive integer +24, there are 4 distinct values of the sums of the divisors in the pairs of complementary divisors. Consequently, there is one value of the largest sum of the divisors in the pairs of complementary positive divisors of the number +24:

$d_{t1} \leq \sqrt{24} $	$d_{t2} \geq \sqrt{24} $	Hyperbolic $x = d_{t1} * d_{t2}$	Hyperbolic $x = d_{t2} * d_{t1}$	$b_{sM} = d_{t2} + d_{t1}$	Parabolic $-d_{t1}(d_{t1} - b_{sM})$	Parabolic $-d_{t2}(d_{t2} - b_{sM})$
1	24	1 * 24	24 * 1	25	-1(1 - 25)	-24(24 - 25)

Figure 45. The largest sum of all pairs of complementary divisors from $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 12, 24\}$ for 24.

Considering the set of its 8 negative divisors in ascending order to be $\{-24, -12, -8, -6, -4, -3, -2, -1\}$ distributed along the Q4 quadrant for the positive integer +24, there are also 4 distinct values of differences between the divisors in the pairs of complementary divisors. Consequently, there is one value of the largest sum the divisors in the pairs of complementary negative divisors for the number +24:

$d_{t1} \leq - \sqrt{24} $	$d_{t2} \geq - \sqrt{24} $	Hyperbolic $x = d_{t1} * d_{t2}$	Hyperbolic $x = d_{t2} * d_{t1}$	$b_{sM} = d_{t2} + d_{t1}$	Parabolic $-d_{t1}(d_{t1} - b_{sM})$	Parabolic $-d_{t2}(d_{t2} - b_{sM})$
-6	-4	-6 * -4	-4 * -6	-10	6(-6 + 10)	4(-4 + 10)

Figure 46. The largest sum of all pairs of complementary divisors from $\{-24, -12, -8, -6, -4, -3, -2, -1\}$ for 24.

Because $25 > -10$, we will consider 25 as being the largest sum of all the pairs of complementary divisors of 24.

Considering the set of its divisors in ascending order to be $\{-4, -3, -2, -1, 6, 8, 12, 24\}$ distributed along the Q3 and Q2 quadrants for the negative integer -24, there are 4 distinct values of differences between the divisors in the pairs of complementary divisors. Consequently, there is one value of the largest sum of the divisors in the pairs of complementary negative and positive divisors for the number -24:

$d_{t1} \geq - \sqrt{24} $	$d_{t2} \geq \sqrt{24} $	Hyperbolic	Hyperbolic	$b_{sM} = d_{t2} + d_{t1}$	Parabolic	Parabolic
----------------------------	---------------------------	------------	------------	----------------------------	-----------	-----------

		$x = d_{t1} * d_{t2}$	$x = d_{t2} * d_{t1}$		$-d_{t1} (d_{t1} - b_{sM})$	$-d_{t2} (d_{t2} - b_{sM})$
-1	24	$-1 * 24$	$24 * -1$	23	$1(-1 - 23)$	$-24(24 - 23)$

Figure 47. The largest sum of all pairs of complementary divisors from $\{-4, -3, -2, -1, 6, 8, 12, 24\}$ for -24 .

Considering the set of its divisors in ascending order to be $\{-24, -12, -8, -6, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ distributed along the Q3 and Q2 quadrants for the negative integer -24 , there are 4 distinct values of differences between the divisors in the pairs of complementary divisors. Consequently, there is one value of the largest sum of the divisors in the pairs of complementary negative and positive divisors for the number -24 :

$d_{t1} \leq - \sqrt{24} $	$d_{t2} \leq \sqrt{24} $	Hyperbolic $x = d_{t1} * d_{t2}$	Hyperbolic $x = d_{t2} * d_{t1}$	$b_{sM} = d_{t2} + d_{t1}$	Parabolic $-d_{t1} (d_{t1} - b_{sM})$	Parabolic $-d_{t2} (d_{t2} - b_{sM})$
-6	4	$-6 * 4$	$4 * -6$	-2	$6(-6 + 2)$	$-4(4 + 2)$

Figure 48. The largest sum of all pairs of complementary divisors from $\{-24, -12, -8, -6, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ for -24 .

Because $23 > -2$, we will consider 23 as being the largest sum of all pairs of complementary divisors of -24 .

10.2 The sequence [C000723](#)

We must analyze 4 cases to get the sequence of the largest sum of the pairs of complementary divisors of the integers.

	Q3	Q2	C00072	Q3	Q2	.	Q3	Q2	.	Q3	Q2	.
	Q1	Q1	3	Q1	Q1	C000723	Q4	Q4	3	Q4	Q4	C000723
	$\sqrt{-A00002}$ 7\	A0000 12	$\sqrt{-A00147}$ 7\	- A0000 12	$\sqrt{A00002}$ 7\	$\sqrt{A00147}$ 7\	$\sqrt{-A00002}$ 7\	A0000 12	$\sqrt{-A00147}$ 7\	- A0000 12	$\sqrt{A00002}$ 7\	$\sqrt{A00147}$ 7\
A2569 58	A00001 2	A0000 27	A02072 5	A0000 12	A000027	A020725	A00002 7	A0000 12	A02072 5	A0000 27	- A000012	- A020725
$x = d_{t1} * d_{t2}$	d_{t1}	d_{t2}	$b_{sM} = d_{t2} - d_{t1}$	d_{t1}	d_{t2}	$b_{sM} = d_{t2} - d_{t1}$	d_{t1}	d_{t2}	$b_{sM} = d_{t2} - d_{t1}$	d_{t1}	d_{t2}	$b_{sM} = d_{t2} - d_{t1}$
-25	-25	1	-24	-1	25	24	-25	1	-24	-1	25	24
-24	-24	1	-23	-1	24	23	-24	1	-23	-1	24	23
-23	-23	1	-22	-1	23	22	-23	1	-22	-1	23	22
-22	-22	1	-21	-1	22	21	-22	1	-21	-1	22	21
-21	-21	1	-20	-1	21	20	-21	1	-20	-1	21	20
-20	-20	1	-19	-1	20	19	-20	1	-19	-1	20	19
-19	-19	1	-18	-1	19	18	-19	1	-18	-1	19	18
-18	-18	1	-17	-1	18	17	-18	1	-17	-1	18	17
-17	-17	1	-16	-1	17	16	-17	1	-16	-1	17	16
-16	-16	1	-15	-1	16	15	-16	1	-15	-1	16	15
-15	-15	1	-14	-1	15	14	-15	1	-14	-1	15	14
-14	-14	1	-13	-1	14	13	-14	1	-13	-1	14	13
-13	-13	1	-12	-1	13	12	-13	1	-12	-1	13	12
-12	-12	1	-11	-1	12	11	-12	1	-11	-1	12	11
-11	-11	1	-10	-1	11	10	-11	1	-10	-1	11	10
-10	-10	1	-9	-1	10	9	-10	1	-9	-1	10	9
-9	-9	1	-8	-1	9	8	-9	1	-8	-1	9	8
-8	-8	1	-7	-1	8	7	-8	1	-7	-1	8	7
-7	-7	1	-6	-1	7	6	-7	1	-6	-1	7	6

-6	-6	1	-5	-1	6	5	-6	1	-5	-1	6	5
-5	-5	1	-4	-1	5	4	-5	1	-4	-1	5	4
-4	-4	1	-3	-1	4	3	-4	1	-3	-1	4	3
-3	-3	1	-2	-1	3	2	-3	1	-2	-1	3	2
-2	-2	1	-1	-1	2	1	-2	1	-1	-1	2	1
-1	-1	1	0	-1	1	0	-1	1	0	-1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	1	2	1	1	2	-1	-1	-2	-1	-1	-2
2	1	2	3	1	2	3	-2	-1	-3	-2	-1	-3
3	1	3	4	1	3	4	-3	-1	-4	-3	-1	-4
4	1	4	5	1	4	5	-4	-1	-5	-4	-1	-5
5	1	5	6	1	5	6	-5	-1	-6	-5	-1	-6
6	1	6	7	1	6	7	-6	-1	-7	-6	-1	-7
7	1	7	8	1	7	8	-7	-1	-8	-7	-1	-8
8	1	8	9	1	8	9	-8	-1	-9	-8	-1	-9
9	1	9	10	1	9	10	-9	-1	-10	-9	-1	-10
10	1	10	11	1	10	11	-10	-1	-11	-10	-1	-11
11	1	11	12	1	11	12	-11	-1	-12	-11	-1	-12
12	1	12	13	1	12	13	-12	-1	-13	-12	-1	-13
13	1	13	14	1	13	14	-13	-1	-14	-13	-1	-14
14	1	14	15	1	14	15	-14	-1	-15	-14	-1	-15
15	1	15	16	1	15	16	-15	-1	-16	-15	-1	-16
16	1	16	17	1	16	17	-16	-1	-17	-16	-1	-17
17	1	17	18	1	17	18	-17	-1	-18	-17	-1	-18
18	1	18	19	1	18	19	-18	-1	-19	-18	-1	-19
19	1	19	20	1	19	20	-19	-1	-20	-19	-1	-20
20	1	20	21	1	20	21	-20	-1	-21	-20	-1	-21
21	1	21	22	1	21	22	-21	-1	-22	-21	-1	-22
22	1	22	23	1	22	23	-22	-1	-23	-22	-1	-23
23	1	23	24	1	23	24	-23	-1	-24	-23	-1	-24
24	1	24	25	1	24	25	-24	-1	-25	-24	-1	-25
25	1	25	26	1	25	26	-25	-1	-26	-25	-1	-26

Figure 49. [C000723](#) Table of 4 possibilities to find the largest sums between the trivial pairs of complementary divisors of the integers $b_{sM} = d_{t2} + d_{t1}$.

There 4 different results for b_{sM} .

The sequences for multiplier and multiplicand are <https://oeis.org/A000027> and <https://oeis.org/A000012>.

The sequences for the products are <https://oeis.org/A001477> and <https://oeis.org/A020725>.

1. $\setminus\text{A000027}\setminus\&0\&\text{A000012} + \text{A000012}\setminus\&0\&\text{A000027} = \setminus\text{A001477}\setminus\&0\&\text{A020725} = \{\dots, -24, -23, -22, -21, -20, -19, -18, -17, -16, -15, -14, -13, -12, -11, -10, -9, -8, -7, -6, -5, -4, -3, -2, -1, 0, 0, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, \dots\}$.
2. $-\text{A000012}\setminus\&0\&\text{A000012} + \setminus\text{A000027}\setminus\&0\&\text{A000027} = \setminus\text{A001477}\setminus\&0\&\text{A020725} = \{\dots, 24, 23, 22, 21, 20, 19, 18, 17, 16, 15, 14, 13, 12, 11, 10, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 0, 0, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, \dots\}$.
3. $\setminus\text{A000027}\setminus\&0\&-\text{A000027} + \text{A000012}\setminus\&0\&-\text{A000012} = \setminus\text{A001477}\setminus\&0\&-\text{A020725} = \{\dots, -24, -23, -22, -21, -20, -19, -18, -17, -16, -15, -14, -13, -12, -11, -10, -9, -8, -7, -6, -5, -4, -3, -2, -1, 0, 0, -2, -3, -4, -5, -6, -7, -8, -9, -10, -11, -12, -13, -14, -15, -16, -17, -18, -19, -20, -21, -22, -23, -24, -25, -26, \dots\}$.
4. $-\text{A000012}\setminus\&0\&-\text{A000027} + \setminus\text{A000027}\setminus\&0\&-\text{A000012} = \setminus\text{A001477}\setminus\&0\&-\text{A020725} = \{\dots, 24, 23, 22, 21, 20, 19, 18, 17, 16, 15, 14, 13, 12, 11, 10, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 0, 0, -2, -3, -4, -5, -6, -7, -8, -9, -10, -11, -12, -13, -14, -15, -16, -17, -18, -19, -20, -21, -22, -23, -24, -25, -26, \dots\}$.

The largest sums of the trivial pairs of complementary divisors of the integers is the sequence [C000723](#) = $\{ \dots, 24, 23, 22, 21, 20, 19, 18, 17, 16, 15, 14, 13, 12, 11, 10, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 0, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, \dots \}$.

See below the graph of this sequence in the XY plane.

Figure 50. [C000723](#) Graph of the largest sums of the trivial pairs of complementary divisors of the integers. The X-axis represents integer numbers, and the Y-axis represents the value of the largest sums.

See the comparison between the largest differences and the largest sums.

Figure 51. Comparison between [C000721](#) the largest differences in red, and [C000723](#) the largest sums in blue.

Both sequences have only non-negative elements.

With respect to the Y-axis which represents integer $x = 0$, the negative part of one is symmetric to the positive part of the other sequence.

So, [C000721](#) = [C000723](#), or [C000721](#) = [C000723](#).

$$\text{C000721} = \text{A020725} \&0\&\text{A001477}$$

$$\text{C000723} = \text{A001477} \&0\&\text{A020725}$$

11 Considerations

Prime numbers have only one pair of complementary divisors. This pair consists only of the trivial pair of complementary divisors of primes. Prime numbers do not have non-trivial divisors. Thus, there is only one sum and one difference between the complementary divisors of any prime number. This sum / difference is both the largest and the smallest sum / difference between its complementary divisors. For any prime P :

$$\begin{aligned} \#b_s[P] &= \#b_d[P] = 1 \\ b_s[P] &= b_{sm}[P] = b_{sM}[P] = d_{t2} + d_{t1} = P + 1 > 0 \\ b_d[P] &= b_{dm}[P] = b_{dM}[P] = d_{t2} - d_{t1} = P - 1 > 0 \end{aligned}$$

Number 1 also has only one pair of complementary divisors. Although the number 1 and the prime numbers have only one trivial pair of complementary divisors, the number 1 has both trivial divisors equal to 1 while any prime number has two different trivial divisors. Thus, every prime number has $b_{dm}[P] = b_{dM}[P] = P - 1 > 0$, but the number 1 has $b_{dm}[1] = b_{dM}[1] = 1 - 1 = 0$:

$$\begin{aligned} \#b_s[1] &= \#b_d[1] = 1 \\ b_s[1] &= b_{sm}[1] = b_{sM}[1] = d_{t2} + d_{t1} = 1 + 1 > 0 \\ b_d[1] &= b_{dm}[1] = b_{dM}[1] = d_{t2} - d_{t1} = 1 - 1 = 0 \end{aligned}$$

This is because number 1 is a square number.

All square numbers $x^2 > 1$ have:

$$\begin{aligned} \#b_s[x^2 > 1] &= \#b_d[x^2 > 1] = \text{https://oeis.org/A161841}[x^2] > 1 \\ b_{sm}[x^2 > 0] &= 2x > 0 \\ b_{sM}[x^2 > 0] &= x^2 + 1 > 0 \\ b_{dm}[x^2 > 0] &= 0 \\ b_{dM}[x^2 > 1] &= x^2 - 1 > 0 \end{aligned}$$

All composite numbers $x = d_1d_2 \neq \text{square}$ have:

$$\begin{aligned} \#b_s[x = d_1d_2 > 4] &= \#b_d[x = d_1d_2 > 4] = \text{https://oeis.org/A161841}[x] > 1 \\ b_{sm}[x = d_1d_2 > 4] &= d_{c1} + d_{c2} = A033676[x] + A033677[x] \\ &= \text{https://oeis.org/A063655}[x] > 1 \\ b_{sM}[x = d_1d_2 > 4] &= d_{t1} + d_{t2} = x + 1 = \text{https://oeis.org/A256958}[x + 1] > 1 \\ b_{dm}[x = d_1d_2 > 4] &= d_{c2} - d_{c1} = A033677[x] - A033677[x] \\ &= \text{https://oeis.org/A056737}[x] > 1 \\ b_{dM}[x = d_1d_2 > 4] &= d_{t2} - d_{t1} = x - 1 = \text{https://oeis.org/A256958}[x - 1] > 1 \end{aligned}$$

Number 0 is the only square number with:

$$\begin{aligned} \#b_s[0] &= \#b_d[0] = \infty \\ b_{sm}[0] &= 0 + 0 = 0 \\ b_{sM}[0] &= 0 + \infty = \infty \\ b_{dm}[0] &= 0 - 0 = 0 \\ b_{dM}[0] &= \infty - 0 = \infty \end{aligned}$$

What distinguishes composites from prime numbers and the number 1 is that all composite numbers have over one pair of complementary divisors.

So, to list all complementary divisors of all integers, it is necessary to do arrangements in arrays.

12 C000720 The central pair of complementary divisors

We define the central pair of complementary divisors $(d_{c1}; d_{c2})$ as those whose absolute value of the difference $b_{dm} = d_{c2} - d_{c1}$ between the two complementary divisors is as small as possible. The central pair of complementary divisors has two divisors as close as possible to each other.

Because of this definition, always d_{c1} of the negative integers will be in Q3 of MID and d_{c2} will be in Q2. For positive integers, d_{c1} and d_{c2} will be in Q1 or both in Q4.

The positive squares have $d_{c2} = d_{c1}$ and the negative squares have $d_{c2} = -d_{c1}$.

All primes have $d_{c1} = d_{t1}$ and $d_{c2} = d_{t2}$. This is a remarkable sieve of primes. This fact also helped us to understand the ideas about MID that we wrote in this study.

The sequence <https://oeis.org/A033676> is the smallest central complementary divisor of positive integer $x > 0$, such as $d_{c1} \leq \sqrt{x}$. They form a sequence, not an array because these divisors are unique for every integer x . They are a subset of the array $d_1 \leq \sqrt{|x|}$ <https://oeis.org/A161906> inside the parabola.

The sequence <https://oeis.org/A033677> is the largest central complementary divisor of positive integer $x > 0$, such as $d_{c2} \geq \sqrt{x}$. They form a sequence, not an array because these divisors also are unique for every integer x . They are a subset of the array $d_2 \geq \sqrt{|x|}$ <https://oeis.org/A161908> outside the parabola.

Based the MID, any positive or negative prime or composite number has two central pairs of complementary divisors. Number 1 or -1 has only one central pair of complementary divisors. Because the number 0 is undefined, but it is a square number, we will define its central pair of complementary divisors $(0; 0)$.

- For integers $x = d_{c1} * d_{c2} = 0$, we have one central pair of complementary divisors: $(0; 0)$.
- For integers $|x| = |d_{c1} * d_{c2}| = 1$, we have two central pairs of complementary divisors: $(-1; 1)$ and $(1; 1)$.
- For integers $|x| = |d_{c1} * d_{c2}| > 1$, we have four central pairs of complementary divisors:
 - Product I for negative integer: $(-A033677; A033676)$
 - Product II for negative integer: $(-A033676; A033677)$
 - Product I for positive integer: $(A033676; A033677)$
 - Product II for positive integer: $(-A033677; -A033676)$

Because of our definition, for $x = 0$, we have one central pair of complementary divisors: $(0; 0)$.

Now, let us see how the central pairs of complementary divisors behave in the MID.

Considering only the increasing direction of the X-axis, then there are 4 possibilities to see the central divisors of all integers in the MID.

See below the location of the divisor's points on the MID. In these cases, we use d_{c1} in light brown #CC9900 color, and d_{c2} in brown #993300.

12.1 $d_{c1} \leq -\sqrt{|x|}$ in Q3, $d_{c1} \leq \sqrt{x}$ in Q1, and $d_{c2} \geq d_{c1}$ in Q2_Q1

Product I: *integers* = $\sqrt{-A033677} \sqrt{A033676} * \sqrt{A033676} \sqrt{A033677}$

Q3		Q2	
Q1		Q1	
\sqrt{-A033677}		\sqrt{A033676}	
A256958	A033676	A256958	A033677
$x = d_{c1} * d_{c2}$	$y = d_{c1}$	$x = d_{c1} * d_{c2}$	$y = d_{c2}$
-25	-5	-25	5
-24	-6	-24	4
-23	-23	-23	1
-22	-11	-22	2
-21	-7	-21	3
-20	-5	-20	4
-19	-19	-19	1
-18	-6	-18	3
-17	-17	-17	1
-16	-4	-16	4
-15	-5	-15	3
-14	-7	-14	2
-13	-13	-13	1
-12	-4	-12	3
-11	-11	-11	1
-10	-5	-10	2
-9	-3	-9	3
-8	-4	-8	2
-7	-7	-7	1
-6	-3	-6	2
-5	-5	-5	1
-4	-2	-4	2
-3	-3	-3	1
-2	-2	-2	1
-1	-1	-1	1
0	0	0	0
1	1	1	1
2	1	2	2
3	1	3	3
4	2	4	2
5	1	5	5
6	2	6	3
7	1	7	7
8	2	8	4
9	3	9	3
10	2	10	5
11	1	11	11
12	3	12	4
13	1	13	13
14	2	14	7
15	3	15	5
16	4	16	4
17	1	17	17
18	3	18	6
19	1	19	19
20	4	20	5
21	3	21	7
22	2	22	11
23	1	23	23
24	4	24	6
25	5	25	5

Figure 52. [C000720](#) Table of coordinates of central divisors for $d_{c1} \leq -\sqrt{|x|}$ in Q3, $d_{c1} \leq \sqrt{x}$ in Q1, and $d_{c2} \geq d_{c1}$ in Q2 and in Q1.

For the negative numbers $x < 0$, d_{c1} starts as $\setminus\text{A033677}\setminus$ in Q3, passes through zero, and continues in the positive numbers $x > 0$ as A033676 in Q1. We will name this sequence as $\setminus\text{A033677}\setminus\&0\&\text{A033676}$ = $\{\dots, -5, -6, -23, -11, -7, -5, -19, -6, -17, -4, -5, -7, -13, -4, -11, -5, -3, -4, -7, -3, -5, -2, -3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 1, 1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 2, 3, 2, 1, 3, 1, 2, 3, 4, 1, 3, 1, 4, 3, 2, 1, 4, 5\dots\}$.

For the negative numbers $x < 0$, d_{c2} starts as $\setminus\text{A033676}\setminus$ in Q2, passes through zero, and continues in the positive numbers $x > 0$ as A033677 in Q1. We will name this sequence as $\setminus\text{A033676}\setminus\&0\&\text{A033677}$ = $\{\dots, 5, 4, 1, 2, 3, 4, 1, 3, 1, 4, 3, 2, 1, 3, 1, 2, 3, 2, 1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 1, 1, 0, 1, 2, 3, 2, 5, 3, 7, 4, 3, 5, 11, 4, 13, 7, 5, 4, 17, 6, 19, 5, 7, 11, 23, 6, 5,, \dots\}$.

Figure 53. [C000720](#) MID display of central divisors for $d_{c1} \leq -\left|\sqrt{|x|}\right|$ in Q3, $d_{c1} \leq \left|\sqrt{x}\right|$ in Q1, and $d_{c2} \geq d_{c1}$ in Q2 and in Q1.

12.2 $d_{c1} \geq -\sqrt{|x|}$ in Q3, $d_{c1} \leq \sqrt{x}$ in Q1, and $d_{c2} \geq d_{c1}$ in Q2_Q1

Product II: integers = $\sqrt{-A033676} \sqrt{A033676} * \sqrt{A033677} \sqrt{A033677}$

	Q3		Q2
	Q1		Q1
	$\sqrt{-A033676}$		$\sqrt{A033677}$
A256958	A033676	A256958	A033677
$x = d_{c1} * d_{c2}$	d_{c1}	$x = d_{c1} * d_{c2}$	d_{c2}
-25	-5	-25	5
-24	-4	-24	6
-23	-1	-23	23
-22	-2	-22	11
-21	-3	-21	7
-20	-4	-20	5
-19	-1	-19	19
-18	-3	-18	6
-17	-1	-17	17
-16	-4	-16	4
-15	-3	-15	5
-14	-2	-14	7
-13	-1	-13	13
-12	-3	-12	4
-11	-1	-11	11
-10	-2	-10	5
-9	-3	-9	3
-8	-2	-8	4
-7	-1	-7	7
-6	-2	-6	3
-5	-1	-5	5
-4	-2	-4	2
-3	-1	-3	3
-2	-1	-2	2
-1	-1	-1	1
0	0	0	0
1	1	1	1
2	1	2	2
3	1	3	3
4	2	4	2
5	1	5	5
6	2	6	3
7	1	7	7
8	2	8	4
9	3	9	3
10	2	10	5
11	1	11	11
12	3	12	4
13	1	13	13
14	2	14	7
15	3	15	5
16	4	16	4
17	1	17	17
18	3	18	6
19	1	19	19
20	4	20	5
21	3	21	7
22	2	22	11
23	1	23	23
24	4	24	6
25	5	25	5

Figure 54. [C000720](#) Table of coordinates of central divisors for $d_{c1} \geq -\sqrt{|x|}$ in Q3, $d_{c1} \leq \sqrt{x}$ in Q1, and $d_{c2} \geq d_{c1}$ in Q2 and in Q1.

For the negative numbers $x < 0$, d_{c1} starts as $\setminus\text{A033676}\setminus$ in Q3, passes through zero, and continues in the positive numbers $x > 0$ as A033676 in Q1. We will name this sequence as $\setminus\text{A033676}\setminus\&0\&\text{A033676} = \{\dots, -5, -4, -1, -2, -3, -4, -1, -3, -1, -4, -3, -2, -1, -3, -1, -2, -3, -2, -1, -2, -1, -2, -1, -1, -1, 0, 1, 1, 1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 2, 3, 2, 1, 3, 1, 2, 3, 4, 1, 3, 1, 4, 3, 2, 1, 4, 5\dots\}$.

For the negative numbers $x < 0$, d_{c2} starts as $\setminus\text{A033677}\setminus$ in Q2, passes through zero, and continues in the positive numbers $x > 0$ as A033677 in Q1. We will name this sequence as $\setminus\text{A033677}\setminus\&0\&\text{A033677} = \{\dots, 5, 6, 23, 11, 7, 5, 19, 6, 17, 4, 5, 7, 13, 4, 11, 5, 3, 4, 7, 3, 5, 2, 3, 2, 1, 0, 1, 2, 3, 2, 5, 3, 7, 4, 3, 5, 11, 4, 13, 7, 5, 4, 17, 6, 19, 5, 7, 11, 23, 6, 5\dots\}$.

Figure 55. C000720 MID display of central divisors for $d_{c1} \geq -\sqrt{|x|}$ in Q3, $d_{c1} \leq \sqrt{x}$ in Q1, and $d_{c2} \geq d_{c1}$ in Q2 and in Q1.

12.3 $d_{c1} \leq -\sqrt{|x|}$ in Q3, $d_{c1} \leq -\sqrt{x}$ in Q4, and $d_{c2} \geq d_{c1}$ in Q2_Q4

Product III: integers = $\sqrt{-A033677} \&0\& -A033677 * \sqrt{A033676} \&0\& -A033676$

	Q3		Q2
	Q4		Q4
	$\sqrt{-A033677}$		$\sqrt{A033676}$
A256958	-A033677	A256958	-A033676
$x = d_{c1} * d_{c2}$	d_{c1}	$x = d_{c1} * d_{c2}$	d_{c2}
-25	-5	-25	5
-24	-6	-24	4
-23	-23	-23	1
-22	-11	-22	2
-21	-7	-21	3
-20	-5	-20	4
-19	-19	-19	1
-18	-6	-18	3
-17	-17	-17	1
-16	-4	-16	4
-15	-5	-15	3
-14	-7	-14	2
-13	-13	-13	1
-12	-4	-12	3
-11	-11	-11	1
-10	-5	-10	2
-9	-3	-9	3
-8	-4	-8	2
-7	-7	-7	1
-6	-3	-6	2
-5	-5	-5	1
-4	-2	-4	2
-3	-3	-3	1
-2	-2	-2	1
-1	-1	-1	1
0	0	0	0
1	-1	1	-1
2	-2	2	-1
3	-3	3	-1
4	-2	4	-2
5	-5	5	-1
6	-3	6	-2
7	-7	7	-1
8	-4	8	-2
9	-3	9	-3
10	-5	10	-2
11	-11	11	-1
12	-4	12	-3
13	-13	13	-1
14	-7	14	-2
15	-5	15	-3
16	-4	16	-4
17	-17	17	-1
18	-6	18	-3
19	-19	19	-1
20	-5	20	-4
21	-7	21	-3
22	-11	22	-2
23	-23	23	-1
24	-6	24	-4
25	-5	25	-5

Figure 56. [C000720](#) Table of coordinates of central divisors for $d_{c1} \leq -\sqrt{|x|}$ in Q3, $d_{c1} \leq \sqrt{x}$ in Q1, and $d_{c2} \geq d_{c1}$ in Q2 and in Q4.

For the negative numbers $x < 0$, d_{c1} starts as $\setminus\text{A033677}\setminus$ in Q3, passes through zero, and continues in the positive numbers $x > 0$ as $-\text{A033677}$ in Q4. We will name this sequence as $\setminus\text{A033677}\&0\&-\text{A033677}\setminus = \{\dots, -5, -6, -23, -11, -7, -5, -19, -6, -17, -4, -5, -7, -13, -4, -11, -5, -3, -4, -7, -3, -5, -2, -3, -2, -1, 0, -1, -2, -3, -2, -5, -3, -7, -4, -3, -5, -11, -4, -13, -7, -5, -4, -17, -6, -19, -5, -7, -11, -23, -6, -5, \dots\}$.

For the negative numbers $x < 0$, d_{c2} starts as $\setminus\text{A033676}\setminus$ in Q2, passes through zero, and continues in the positive numbers $x > 0$ as $-\text{A033676}$ in Q4. We will name this sequence as $\setminus\text{A033676}\&0\&-\text{A033676}\setminus = \{\dots, 5, 4, 1, 2, 3, 4, 1, 3, 1, 4, 3, 2, 1, 3, 1, 2, 3, 2, 1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 1, 1, 0, -1, -1, -1, -2, -1, -2, -1, -2, -3, -2, -1, -3, -1, -2, -3, -4, -1, -3, -1, -4, -3, -2, -1, -4, -5, \dots\}$.

Figure 57. [C000720](#) MID display of central divisors for $d_{c1} \leq -\sqrt{|x|}$ in Q3, $d_{c1} \leq \sqrt{x}$ in Q1, and $d_{c2} \geq d_{c1}$ in Q2 and in Q4.

12.4 $d_{c1} \geq -|\sqrt{|x|}|$ in Q3, $d_{c1} \leq -|\sqrt{x}|$ in Q4, and $d_{c2} \geq d_{c1}$ in Q2_Q4

Product IV: integers = $-\sqrt{-A033676} \sqrt{-A033677} * \sqrt{A033677} \sqrt{-A033676}$

	Q3		Q2
	Q4		Q4
	$\sqrt{-A033676}$		$\sqrt{A033677}$
A256958	$-A033677$	A256958	$-A033676$
$x = d_{c1} * d_{c2}$	d_{c1}	$x = d_{c1} * d_{c2}$	d_{c2}
-25	-5	-25	5
-24	-4	-24	6
-23	-1	-23	23
-22	-2	-22	11
-21	-3	-21	7
-20	-4	-20	5
-19	-1	-19	19
-18	-3	-18	6
-17	-1	-17	17
-16	-4	-16	4
-15	-3	-15	5
-14	-2	-14	7
-13	-1	-13	13
-12	-3	-12	4
-11	-1	-11	11
-10	-2	-10	5
-9	-3	-9	3
-8	-2	-8	4
-7	-1	-7	7
-6	-2	-6	3
-5	-1	-5	5
-4	-2	-4	2
-3	-1	-3	3
-2	-1	-2	2
-1	-1	-1	1
0	0	0	0
1	-1	1	-1
2	-2	2	-1
3	-3	3	-1
4	-2	4	-2
5	-5	5	-1
6	-3	6	-2
7	-7	7	-1
8	-4	8	-2
9	-3	9	-3
10	-5	10	-2
11	-11	11	-1
12	-4	12	-3
13	-13	13	-1
14	-7	14	-2
15	-5	15	-3
16	-4	16	-4
17	-17	17	-1
18	-6	18	-3
19	-19	19	-1
20	-5	20	-4
21	-7	21	-3
22	-11	22	-2
23	-23	23	-1
24	-6	24	-4
25	-5	25	-5

Figure 58. [C000720](#) Table of coordinates of central divisors for $d_{c1} \geq -|\sqrt{|x|}|$ in Q3, $d_{c1} \leq -|\sqrt{x}|$ in Q1, and $d_{c2} \geq d_{c1}$ in Q2 and in Q4.

For the negative numbers $x < 0$, d_{c1} starts as $\setminus\text{A033676}\setminus$ in Q3, passes through zero, and continues in the positive numbers $x > 0$ as A033677 in Q4. We will name this sequence as $\setminus\text{A033676}\setminus\&0\&\text{A033677} = \{\dots, -5, -4, -1, -2, -3, -4, -1, -3, -1, -4, -3, -2, -1, -3, -1, -2, -3, -2, -1, -2, -1, -2, -1, -1, -1, 0, -1, -2, -3, -2, -5, -3, -7, -4, -3, -5, -11, -4, -13, -7, -5, -4, -17, -6, -19, -5, -7, -11, -23, -6, -5, \dots\}$.

For the negative numbers $x < 0$, d_{c2} starts as $\setminus\text{A033677}\setminus$ in Q2, passes through zero, and continues in the positive numbers $x > 0$ as A033676 in Q4. We will name this sequence as $\setminus\text{A033677}\setminus\&0\&\text{A033676} = \{\dots, 5, 6, 23, 11, 7, 5, 19, 6, 17, 4, 5, 7, 13, 4, 11, 5, 3, 4, 7, 3, 5, 2, 3, 2, 1, 0, -1, -1, -1, -2, -1, -2, -1, -2, -3, -2, -1, -3, -1, -2, -3, -4, -1, -3, -1, -4, -3, -2, -1, -4, -5, \dots\}$.

Figure 59. [C000720](#) MID display of central divisors for $d_{c1} \geq -\sqrt{|x|}$ in Q3, $d_{c1} \leq -\sqrt{x}$ in Q1, and $d_{c2} \geq d_{c1}$ in Q2 and in Q4.

12.5 General view

General view:

Figure 60. [C000720](#) The central pair of complementary divisors: in light brown d_{c1} , and in brown d_{c2} .

For example, the central pair of complementary divisors of the integer 24 is

1. In Q1: the largest divisor $d_1 \leq \sqrt{|24|}$ noted as $d_{c1} = 4$ and the smallest divisor $d_2 \geq \sqrt{|24|}$ noted as $d_{c2} = 6$.
2. In Q4: the largest divisor $d_1 \leq -\sqrt{|24|}$ noted as $d_{c1} = -6$ and the smallest divisor $d_2 \geq -\sqrt{|24|}$ noted as $d_{c2} = -4$.

There are 2 pairs of complementary divisors of +24: (4; 6) and (-6; -4).

The central pair of complementary divisors of the integer -24 is

1. In Q2 and Q3: the largest divisor $d_1 \leq -\sqrt{|24|}$ noted as $d_{c1} = -6$ and the smallest divisor $d_2 \leq +\sqrt{|24|}$ noted as $d_{c2} = 4$.
2. In Q2 and Q3: the smallest divisor $d_1 \geq -\sqrt{|24|}$ noted as $d_{c1} = -4$ and the smallest divisor $d_2 \geq \sqrt{|24|}$ noted as $d_{c2} = 6$.

There are 2 pairs of complementary divisors of -24 : $(-6; 4)$ and $(-4; 6)$.

13 C000722 The smallest difference between all complementary divisors

Let us define b_{dm} as the smallest (minimum absolute value) difference between all pairs of complementary divisors of an integer $x = d_{c1} * d_{c2}$ and $d_{c2} \geq d_{c1}$ such that:

$$b_{dm} = (\text{smallest } d_2) - (\text{largest } d_1) \geq 0$$

$$b_{dm} = d_{c2} - d_{c1} \geq 0$$

To comply with the smallest difference:

- d_{c1} is the smallest central complementary divisor. It is the largest positive divisor of the integer $x \geq 0$, such as $d_{c1} \leq \sqrt{|x|}$. It is the sequence <https://oeis.org/A033676>.
- d_{c2} is the largest central complementary divisor. It is the smallest positive divisor of the integer $x \geq 0$, such as $\sqrt{|x|} \leq d_{c2} \leq x$. It is the sequence <https://oeis.org/A033677>.

The difference between the positive divisors of the central pair of complementary divisors is

$$b_{dm} = \text{A033677}[x > 0] - \text{A033676}[x > 0] = \text{A056737}[x > 0]$$

They are in the range delimited by the green lines of **Error! Reference source not found.**

Because $x = d_{c1} * d_{c2}$, then $x = d_{c2} * d_{c1}$. We call these two forms the hyperbolic form.

From each of the two hyperbolic forms, it is possible to find two parabolic forms:

$$x = d_{c1}(d_{c1} + b_{dm}) = d_{c1}^2 + b_{dm}d_{c1}$$

$$x = d_{c2}(d_{c2} - b_{dm}) = d_{c2}^2 - b_{dm}d_{c2}$$

The importance of defining the minimum difference between the divisors in pair of complementary divisors b_{dm} is because:

1. The central pair of complementary divisors is unique for each integer.
2. The smallest difference between the central complementary divisors b_{dm} ranks all integers (positive and negative, including zero) according to the parabolic and hyperbolic formulas:

$$d_{c1}^2 + b_{dm}d_{c1} = d_{c1}(d_{c1} + b_{dm}) = d_{c1} * d_{c2}$$

$$d_{c2}^2 - b_{dm}d_{c2} = d_{c2}(d_{c2} - b_{dm}) = d_{c2} * d_{c1}$$

For example, any square number has two central divisors equal. The central divisors are equal to the square root of the square number. Here, the minimum difference between them is zero.

$$b_{dm}(\text{any square number}) = 0$$

13.1 Example for integers +24 and -24

Integer 24 has eight positive divisors given by $\{1,2,3,4,6,8,12,24\}$. There are 4 pairs of distinct, complementary positive divisors. Consequently, there is one value of the smallest

difference between the divisors in the pairs of complementary positive divisors for the number 24. The value of the smallest difference between the divisors in the pairs of complementary divisors for the number +24 is:

$d_{c1} \leq \sqrt{24}$	$d_{c2} \geq \sqrt{24}$	Hyperbolic $x = d_{c1} * d_{c2}$	Hyperbolic $x = d_{c2} * d_{c1}$	$b_{dm} = d_{c2} - d_{c1}$	Parabolic $d_{c1} (d_{c1} + b_{dm})$	Parabolic $d_{c2} (d_{c2} - b_{dm})$
4	6	4 * 6	6 * 4	2	4(4 + 2)	6(6 - 2)

Figure 61. The smallest difference of all pairs of complementary divisors from {1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 12, 24} for 24.

Integer 24 has eight negative divisors given by {-24, -12, -8, -6, -4, -3, -2, -1}. There are 4 pairs of distinct complementary negative divisors. Consequently, there is one value of the smallest difference between the divisors in the pairs of complementary negative divisors for the number 24:

Considering the set of its 8 negative divisors in ascending order to be {-24, -12, -8, -6, -4, -3, -2, -1} there are 4 distinct values of differences between the divisors in the pairs of complementary divisors for the positive integer +24. The value of the smallest difference between the divisors in the pairs of complementary divisors for the number +24 is:

$d_{c1} \leq -\sqrt{24}$	$d_{c2} \geq -\sqrt{24}$	Hyperbolic $x = d_{c1} * d_{c2}$	Hyperbolic $x = d_{c2} * d_{c1}$	$b_{dm} = d_{c2} - d_{c1}$	Parabolic $d_{c1} (d_{c1} + b_{dm})$	Parabolic $d_{c2} (d_{c2} - b_{dm})$
-6	-4	-6 * -4	-4 * -6	2	-6(-6 + 2)	-4(-4 - 2)

Figure 62. The smallest difference of all pairs of complementary divisors from {-24, -12, -8, -6, -4, -3, -2, -1} for 24.

Considering the set of its divisors in ascending order to be {-4, -3, -2, -1, 6, 8, 12, 24}, there are 4 distinct values of differences between the divisors in the pairs of complementary divisors for the negative integer -24. The value of the smallest difference between the divisors in the pairs of complementary divisors for the number -24 is:

$d_{c1} \geq -\sqrt{24}$	$d_{c2} \geq \sqrt{24}$	Hyperbolic $x = d_{c1} * d_{c2}$	Hyperbolic $x = d_{c2} * d_{c1}$	$b_{dm} = d_{c2} - d_{c1}$	Parabolic $d_{c1} (d_{c1} + b_{dm})$	Parabolic $d_{c2} (d_{c2} - b_{dm})$
-4	6	-4 * 6	6 * -4	10	-4(-4 + 10)	6(6 - 10)

Figure 63. The smallest difference of all pairs of complementary divisors from {-4, -3, -2, -1, 6, 8, 12, 24} for -24.

Considering the set of its divisors in ascending order to be {-24, -12, -8, -6, 1, 2, 3, 4}, there are 4 distinct values of differences between the divisors in the pairs of complementary divisors for the negative integer -24. The value of the smallest difference between the divisors in the pairs of complementary divisors for the number -24 is:

$d_{c1} \leq -\sqrt{24}$	$d_{c2} \leq \sqrt{24}$	Hyperbolic $x = d_{c1} * d_{c2}$	Hyperbolic $x = d_{c2} * d_{c1}$	$b_{dm} = d_{c2} - d_{c1}$	Parabolic $d_{c1} (d_{c1} + b_{dm})$	Parabolic $d_{c2} (d_{c2} - b_{dm})$
-6	4	-6 * 4	4 * -6	10	-6(-6 + 10)	4(4 - 10)

Figure 64. The smallest difference of all pairs of complementary divisors from {-24, -12, -8, -6, 1, 2, 3, 4} for -24.

13.2 The sequence [C000722](#)

We must analyze 4 cases to get the sequence of the smallest difference of the pairs of complementary divisors of the integers.

	Q3	Q2	C000722									
	Q1	Q1	C000722	Q1	Q1	C000722	Q4	Q4	C000722	Q4	Q4	C000722
	$\sqrt{-A033677}$	$\sqrt{A033676}$	$\sqrt{A063655}$	$\sqrt{-A033676}$	$\sqrt{A033677}$	$\sqrt{A063655}$	$\sqrt{-A033676}$	$\sqrt{A033677}$	$\sqrt{A063655}$	$\sqrt{-A033676}$	$\sqrt{A033677}$	$\sqrt{A063655}$
	&0&	&0&	&0&	&0&	&0&	&0&	&0&	&0&	&0&	&0&	&0&	&0&
A256958	A033676	A033677	A056737	A033676	A033677	A056737	-A033677	-A033676	A056737	-A033677	-A033676	A056737
$x = d_{c1} * d_{c2}$	d_{c1}	d_{c2}	$b_{dm} = dc2 - dc1$	d_{c1}	d_{c2}	$b_{dm} = dc2 - dc1$	d_{c1}	d_{c2}	$b_{dm} = dc2 - dc1$	d_{c1}	d_{c2}	$b_{dm} = dc2 - dc1$
-25	-5	5	10	-5	5	10	-5	5	10	-5	5	10
-24	-6	4	10	-4	6	10	-6	4	10	-4	6	10
-23	-23	1	24	-1	23	24	-23	1	24	-1	23	24
-22	-11	2	13	-2	11	13	-11	2	13	-2	11	13
-21	-7	3	10	-3	7	10	-7	3	10	-3	7	10
-20	-5	4	9	-4	5	9	-5	4	9	-4	5	9
-19	-19	1	20	-1	19	20	-19	1	20	-1	19	20
-18	-6	3	9	-3	6	9	-6	3	9	-3	6	9
-17	-17	1	18	-1	17	18	-17	1	18	-1	17	18
-16	-4	4	8	-4	4	8	-4	4	8	-4	4	8
-15	-5	3	8	-3	5	8	-5	3	8	-3	5	8
-14	-7	2	9	-2	7	9	-7	2	9	-2	7	9
-13	-13	1	14	-1	13	14	-13	1	14	-1	13	14
-12	-4	3	7	-3	4	7	-4	3	7	-3	4	7
-11	-11	1	12	-1	11	12	-11	1	12	-1	11	12
-10	-5	2	7	-2	5	7	-5	2	7	-2	5	7
-9	-3	3	6	-3	3	6	-3	3	6	-3	3	6
-8	-4	2	6	-2	4	6	-4	2	6	-2	4	6
-7	-7	1	8	-1	7	8	-7	1	8	-1	7	8
-6	-3	2	5	-2	3	5	-3	2	5	-2	3	5
-5	-5	1	6	-1	5	6	-5	1	6	-1	5	6
-4	-2	2	4	-2	2	4	-2	2	4	-2	2	4
-3	-3	1	4	-1	3	4	-3	1	4	-1	3	4
-2	-2	1	3	-1	2	3	-2	1	3	-1	2	3
-1	-1	1	2	-1	1	2	-1	1	2	-1	1	2
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	1	0	1	1	0	-1	-1	0	-1	-1	0
2	1	2	1	1	2	1	-2	-1	1	-2	-1	1
3	1	3	2	1	3	2	-3	-1	2	-3	-1	2
4	2	2	0	2	2	0	-2	-2	0	-2	-2	0
5	1	5	4	1	5	4	-5	-1	4	-5	-1	4
6	2	3	1	2	3	1	-3	-2	1	-3	-2	1
7	1	7	6	1	7	6	-7	-1	6	-7	-1	6
8	2	4	2	2	4	2	-4	-2	2	-4	-2	2
9	3	3	0	3	3	0	-3	-3	0	-3	-3	0
10	2	5	3	2	5	3	-5	-2	3	-5	-2	3
11	1	11	10	1	11	10	-11	-1	10	-11	-1	10
12	3	4	1	3	4	1	-4	-3	1	-4	-3	1
13	1	13	12	1	13	12	-13	-1	12	-13	-1	12
14	2	7	5	2	7	5	-7	-2	5	-7	-2	5
15	3	5	2	3	5	2	-5	-3	2	-5	-3	2
16	4	4	0	4	4	0	-4	-4	0	-4	-4	0
17	1	17	16	1	17	16	-17	-1	16	-17	-1	16
18	3	6	3	3	6	3	-6	-3	3	-6	-3	3
19	1	19	18	1	19	18	-19	-1	18	-19	-1	18
20	4	5	1	4	5	1	-5	-4	1	-5	-4	1
21	3	7	4	3	7	4	-7	-3	4	-7	-3	4
22	2	11	9	2	11	9	-11	-2	9	-11	-2	9
23	1	23	22	1	23	22	-23	-1	22	-23	-1	22
24	4	6	2	4	6	2	-6	-4	2	-6	-4	2
25	5	5	0	5	5	0	-5	-5	0	-5	-5	0

Figure 65. [C000722](#) Table of 4 possibilities to find the smallest differences between the central pairs of complementary divisors of the integers $b_{dm} = d_{c2} + d_{c1}$.

There 4 different results for b_{dm} :

The sequences for multiplier and multiplicand are <https://oeis.org/A033676> and <https://oeis.org/A033677>.

The sequences for the products are <https://oeis.org/A063655> and <https://oeis.org/A056737>.

1. $\backslash A033676 \backslash \&0 \& A033677 - \backslash -A033677 \backslash \&0 \& A033676 = \backslash A063655 \backslash \&0 \& A056737$
2. $\backslash A033677 \backslash \&0 \& A033677 - \backslash -A033676 \backslash \&0 \& A033676 = \backslash A063655 \backslash \&0 \& A056737$
3. $\backslash A033677 \backslash \&0 \& -A033676 - \backslash -A033676 \backslash \&0 \& -A033677 = \backslash A063655 \backslash \&0 \& A056737$
4. $\backslash A033677 \backslash \&0 \& -A033676 - \backslash -A033676 \backslash \&0 \& -A033677 = \backslash A063655 \backslash \&0 \& A056737$

There is only one solution for b_{dm} in all 4 cases.

The smallest differences between the central pairs of complementary divisors of the integers is the sequence [C000722](#) = $\backslash A063655 \backslash \&0 \& A056737 = \{ \dots, 10, 10, 24, 13, 10, 9, 20, 9, 18, 8, 8, 9, 14, 7, 12, 7, 6, 6, 8, 5, 6, 4, 4, 3, 2, 0, 0, 1, 2, 0, 4, 1, 6, 2, 0, 3, 10, 1, 12, 5, 2, 0, 16, 3, 18, 1, 4, 9, 22, 2, 0, \dots \}$.

See below the graph of this sequence in the XY plane.

Figure 66. [C000722](#) Graph of the smallest differences of the central pairs of complementary divisors of the integers. The X-axis represents integer numbers, and the Y-axis represents the value of the largest sums.

14 C000724 The smallest sum of all complementary divisors

Let us define b_{sm} as the smallest (minimum value) sum between all pairs of complementary divisors of an integer $x = d_{c1} * d_{c2}$ and $d_{c2} \geq d_{c1}$ such that:

$$b_{sm} = (\text{smallest } d_2) + (\text{largest } d_1)$$

$$b_{sm} = d_{c2} + d_{c1}$$

To comply with the smallest sum:

- d_{c1} is the smallest central complementary divisor. It is the largest positive divisor of the integer $x \geq 0$, such as $d_{c1} \leq \sqrt{|x|}$. It is the sequence <https://oeis.org/A033676>.

- d_{c2} is the largest central complementary divisor. It is the smallest positive divisor of the integer $x \geq 0$, such as $\sqrt{|x|} \leq d_{c2} \leq x$. It is the sequence <https://oeis.org/A033677>.

The sum of the positive divisors of the central pair of complementary divisors is

$$b_{sm} = A033677[x > 0] + A033676[x > 0] = A063655[x > 0]$$

Because $x = d_{c1} * d_{c2}$, then $x = d_{c2} * d_{c1}$. We call these two forms the hyperbolic form.

From each of the two hyperbolic forms, it is possible to find two parabolic forms:

$$x = -d_{c1}(d_{c1} - b_{sm}) = -d_{c1}^2 + b_{sm}d_{c1}$$

$$x = -d_{c2}(d_{c2} - b_{sm}) = -d_{c2}^2 + b_{sm}d_{c2}$$

For example, any square number has two central divisors equal. The central divisors are equal to the square root of the positive square number. Here, the minimum sum of the complementary divisors is

$$b_{sm}(x^2) = 2 * |x| < x^2 \pm 1$$

14.1 Example for integers +24 and -24

Considering the set of its 8 positive divisors in ascending order to be {1, 2,3,4,6, 8, 12, 24} distributed along the Q1 quadrant for the positive integer +24, there are 4 distinct values of the sums of the divisors in the pairs of complementary divisors. Consequently, there is one value of the smallest sum the divisors in the pairs of complementary positive divisors for the number +24:

d_{c1} $\leq \sqrt{24} $	d_{c2} $\geq \sqrt{24} $	Hyperbolic x $= d_{c1} * d_{c2}$	Hyperbolic x $= d_{c2} * d_{c1}$	b_{sm} $= d_{c2} + d_{c1}$	Parabolic $-d_{c1}(d_{c1} - b_{sm})$	Parabolic $-d_{c2}(d_{c2} - b_{sm})$
4	6	4 * 6	6 * 4	10	-4(4 - 10)	-6(6 - 10)

Figure 67. The smallest sum of all pairs of complementary divisors from {1, 2,3,4,6, 8, 12, 24} for 24.

Considering the set of its 8 negative divisors in ascending order to be {-24, -12, -8, -6, -4, -3, -2, -1} distributed along the Q4 quadrant for the positive integer +24, there are also 4 distinct values of the sums of the divisors in the pairs of complementary divisors. Consequently, there is one value of the smallest sum the divisors in the pairs of complementary negative divisors for the number +24:

d_{c1} $\leq - \sqrt{24} $	d_{c2} $\geq - \sqrt{24} $	Hyperbolic x $= d_{c1} * d_{c2}$	Hyperbolic x $= d_{c2} * d_{c1}$	b_{sm} $= d_{c2} + d_{c1}$	Parabolic $-d_{c1}(d_{c1} - b_{sm})$	Parabolic $-d_{c2}(d_{c2} - b_{sm})$
-24	-1	-24 * -1	-1 * -24	-25	24(-24 + 25)	1(-1 + 25)

Figure 68. The smallest sum of all pairs of complementary divisors from {-24, -12, -8, -6, -4, -3, -2, -1} for 24.

Because $-25 < 10$, we will consider -25 as being the smallest sum of all pairs of complementary divisors of 24.

Considering the set of its divisors in ascending order to be {-4, -3, -2, -1, 6, 8, 12, 24} distributed along the Q3 and Q2 quadrants for the negative integer -24, there are 4 distinct values of sums of the divisors in the pairs of complementary divisors. Consequently, there is one value

of the smallest sum the divisors in the pairs of complementary positive and negative divisors for the number -24 :

d_{c1} $\geq - \sqrt{24} $	d_{c2} $\geq \sqrt{24} $	Hyperbolic x $= d_{c1} * d_{c2}$	Hyperbolic x $= d_{c2} * d_{c1}$	b_{sm} $= d_{c2} + d_{c1}$	Parabolic $-d_{c1} (d_{c1}$ $- b_{sm})$	Parabolic $-d_{c2} (d_{c2}$ $- b_{sm})$
-4	6	$-4 * 6$	$6 * -4$	2	$4(-4 - 2)$	$-6(6 - 2)$

Figure 69. The smallest sum of all pairs of complementary divisors from $\{-4, -3, -2, -1, 6, 8, 12, 24\}$ for -24 .

Considering the set of its divisors in ascending order to be $\{-24, -12, -8, -6, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ also distributed along the Q3 and Q2 quadrants for the negative integer -24 , there are 4 distinct values of sums of the divisors in the pairs of complementary divisors. Consequently, there is one value of the smallest sum the divisors in the pairs of complementary positive and negative divisors for the number -24 :

d_{c1} $\leq - \sqrt{24} $	d_{c2} $\leq \sqrt{24} $	Hyperbolic x $= d_{c1} * d_{c2}$	Hyperbolic x $= d_{c2} * d_{c1}$	b_{sm} $= d_{c2} + d_{c1}$	Parabolic $-d_{c1} (d_{c1}$ $- b_{sm})$	Parabolic $-d_{c2} (d_{c2}$ $- b_{sm})$
-24	1	$-24 * 1$	$1 * -24$	-23	$24(-24 + 23)$	$-1(1 + 23)$

Figure 70. The smallest sum of all pairs of complementary divisors from $\{-24, -12, -8, -6, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ for -24 .

Because $-23 < 2$, we will consider -23 as being the smallest sum of all pairs of complementary divisors of -24 .

14.2 The sequence [C000724](#)

We must analyze 4 cases to get the sequence of the smallest sum of the pairs of complementary divisors of the integers.

	Q3	Q2	C00072 4	Q3	Q2	C00072 4	Q3	Q2	C00072 4	Q3	Q2	C00072 4
	Q1	Q1		Q1	Q1		Q4	Q4		Q4	Q4	
	$\sqrt{-A03367}$ 7\	$\sqrt{A033676}$ 7\	$\sqrt{-A05673}$ 7\	$\sqrt{-A033676}$ 6\	$\sqrt{A033677}$ 7\	$\sqrt{A056737}$ 3\	$\sqrt{-A033676}$ 6\	$\sqrt{A033677}$ 7\	$\sqrt{-A056737}$ 7\	$\sqrt{-A033676}$ 6\	$\sqrt{A033677}$ 7\	$\sqrt{A056737}$ 3\
	&0&	&0&	&0&	&0&	&0&	&0&	&0&	&0&	&0&	&0&	&0&	&0&
A2569 58	A03367 6	A03367 7	A06365 5	A03367 6	A03367 7	A06365 5	A03367 7	A03367 6	A06365 5	A03367 7	A03367 6	A06365 5
x $= d_{c1}$ $* d_{c2}$	d_{c1}	d_{c2}	b_{sm} $= d_{c2}$ $+ d_{c1}$	d_{c1}	d_{c2}	b_{sm} $= d_{c2}$ $+ d_{c1}$	d_{c1}	d_{c2}	b_{sm} $= d_{c2}$ $+ d_{c1}$	d_{c1}	d_{c2}	b_{sm} $= d_{c2}$ $+ d_{c1}$
-25	-5	5	0	-5	5	0	-5	5	0	-5	5	0
-24	-6	4	-2	-4	6	2	-6	4	-2	-4	6	2
-23	-23	1	-22	-1	23	22	-23	1	-22	-1	23	22
-22	-11	2	-9	-2	11	9	-11	2	-9	-2	11	9
-21	-7	3	-4	-3	7	4	-7	3	-4	-3	7	4
-20	-5	4	-1	-4	5	1	-5	4	-1	-4	5	1
-19	-19	1	-18	-1	19	18	-19	1	-18	-1	19	18
-18	-6	3	-3	-3	6	3	-6	3	-3	-3	6	3
-17	-17	1	-16	-1	17	16	-17	1	-16	-1	17	16
-16	-4	4	0	-4	4	0	-4	4	0	-4	4	0
-15	-5	3	-2	-3	5	2	-5	3	-2	-3	5	2
-14	-7	2	-5	-2	7	5	-7	2	-5	-2	7	5
-13	-13	1	-12	-1	13	12	-13	1	-12	-1	13	12

-12	-4	3	-1	-3	4	1	-4	3	-1	-3	4	1
-11	-11	1	-10	-1	11	10	-11	1	-10	-1	11	10
-10	-5	2	-3	-2	5	3	-5	2	-3	-2	5	3
-9	-3	3	0	-3	3	0	-3	3	0	-3	3	0
-8	-4	2	-2	-2	4	2	-4	2	-2	-2	4	2
-7	-7	1	-6	-1	7	6	-7	1	-6	-1	7	6
-6	-3	2	-1	-2	3	1	-3	2	-1	-2	3	1
-5	-5	1	-4	-1	5	4	-5	1	-4	-1	5	4
-4	-2	2	0	-2	2	0	-2	2	0	-2	2	0
-3	-3	1	-2	-1	3	2	-3	1	-2	-1	3	2
-2	-2	1	-1	-1	2	1	-2	1	-1	-1	2	1
-1	-1	1	0	-1	1	0	-1	1	0	-1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	1	2	1	1	2	-1	-1	-2	-1	-1	-2
2	1	2	3	1	2	3	-2	-1	-3	-2	-1	-3
3	1	3	4	1	3	4	-3	-1	-4	-3	-1	-4
4	2	2	4	2	2	4	-2	-2	-4	-2	-2	-4
5	1	5	6	1	5	6	-5	-1	-6	-5	-1	-6
6	2	3	5	2	3	5	-3	-2	-5	-3	-2	-5
7	1	7	8	1	7	8	-7	-1	-8	-7	-1	-8
8	2	4	6	2	4	6	-4	-2	-6	-4	-2	-6
9	3	3	6	3	3	6	-3	-3	-6	-3	-3	-6
10	2	5	7	2	5	7	-5	-2	-7	-5	-2	-7
11	1	11	12	1	11	12	-11	-1	-12	-11	-1	-12
12	3	4	7	3	4	7	-4	-3	-7	-4	-3	-7
13	1	13	14	1	13	14	-13	-1	-14	-13	-1	-14
14	2	7	9	2	7	9	-7	-2	-9	-7	-2	-9
15	3	5	8	3	5	8	-5	-3	-8	-5	-3	-8
16	4	4	8	4	4	8	-4	-4	-8	-4	-4	-8
17	1	17	18	1	17	18	-17	-1	-18	-17	-1	-18
18	3	6	9	3	6	9	-6	-3	-9	-6	-3	-9
19	1	19	20	1	19	20	-19	-1	-20	-19	-1	-20
20	4	5	9	4	5	9	-5	-4	-9	-5	-4	-9
21	3	7	10	3	7	10	-7	-3	-10	-7	-3	-10
22	2	11	13	2	11	13	-11	-2	-13	-11	-2	-13
23	1	23	24	1	23	24	-23	-1	-24	-23	-1	-24
24	4	6	10	4	6	10	-6	-4	-10	-6	-4	-10
25	5	5	10	5	5	10	-5	-5	-10	-5	-5	-10

Figure 71. [C000724](#) Table of 4 possibilities to find the smallest differences between the central pairs of complementary divisors of the integers $b_{sm} = d_{c2} + d_{c1}$.

There 4 different results for b_{sm} :

The sequences for multiplier and multiplicand are <https://oeis.org/A033676> and <https://oeis.org/A033677>.

The sequences for the products are <https://oeis.org/A063655> and <https://oeis.org/A056737>.

1. $\sqrt{-A033677 \cdot A033676} + \sqrt{A033676 \cdot A033677} = \sqrt{-A056737 \cdot A063655}$
2. $\sqrt{-A033676 \cdot A033676} + \sqrt{A033677 \cdot A033677} = \sqrt{-A056737 \cdot A063655}$
3. $\sqrt{-A033676 \cdot -A033677} + \sqrt{A033677 \cdot -A033676} = \sqrt{-A056737 \cdot -A063655}$
4. $\sqrt{-A033676 \cdot -A033677} + \sqrt{A033677 \cdot -A033676} = \sqrt{A056737 \cdot -A063655}$

There is only one solution for b_{sm} in all 4 cases.

The smallest sums between the central pairs of complementary divisors of the integers is the sequence [C000724](#) = $\sqrt{-A056737 \cdot -A063655} = \{\dots, 0, -2, -22, -9, -4, -1, -18, -3, -16, 0, -2, -5, -12, -1, -10, -3, 0, -2, -6, -1, -4, 0, -2, -1, 0, 0, -2, -3, -4, -4, -6, -5, -8, -6, -6, -7, -12, -7, -14, -9, -8, -8, -18, -9, -20, -9, -10, -13, -24, -10, -10, \dots\}$.

See below the graph of this sequence in the XY plane.

Figure 72. [C000724](#) Graph of the smallest sums of the central pairs of complementary divisors of the integers. The X-axis represents integer numbers, and the Y-axis represents the value of the largest sums

See the comparison between the smallest differences and the smallest sums.

Figure 73. Comparison between [C000722](#) the smallest differences in red, and [C000724](#) the smallest sums in blue.

The sequence [C000722](#) with the smallest differences has only positive elements. The sequence [C000724](#) with the smallest sums has only negative elements.

$C000722 = \sqrt{A063655} \& \& A056737 = \{ \dots, 10, 10, 24, 13, 10, 9, 20, 9, 18, 8, 8, 9, 14, 7, 12, 7, 6, 6, 8, 5, 6, 4, 4, 3, 2, 0, 0, 1, 2, 0, 4, 1, 6, 2, 0, 3, 10, 1, 12, 5, 2, 0, 16, 3, 18, 1, 4, 9, 22, 2, 0, \dots \}.$

$C000724 = \sqrt{-A056737} \& \& -A063655 = \{ \dots, 0, -2, -22, -9, -4, -1, -18, -3, -16, 0, -2, -5, -12, -1, -10, -3, 0, -2, -6, -1, -4, 0, -2, -1, 0, -2, -3, -4, -4, -6, -5, -8, -6, -6, -7, -12, -7, -14, -9, -8, -8, -18, -9, -20, -9, -10, -13, -24, -10, -10, \dots \}.$

There is a symmetry between the sequences [C000722](#) and [C000724](#) when we simultaneously use the X and Y axes:

$$C000722 = -C000724$$

$$C000724 = -C000722$$

15 Study of sequences C000721 C000722 C000723 C000724

Let us see the sums and the differences of divisors from pairs of complementary divisors. See bigger picture at [C000721 C000722 C000723 C000724](#).

Figure 74. Comparison between [C000721](#) the largest differences and [C000722](#) the smallest differences both in red, and [C000723](#) the largest sums and [C000724](#) the smallest sums in blue.

Now, let's look in more detail at the sequences [C000722](#) the smallest differences, and [C000724](#) the smallest sums.

Figure 75. [C000722 \(A056737\)](#) the smallest differences in red, and [C000724 \(A063655\)](#) the smallest sums in blue.

When we use the positive and negative square numbers to make demarcations along the X-axis, we can notice a repetition of some patterns that periodically follow the square numbers.

For example, for every square number there is a square number minus 1. In the smallest differences, there is always the point $(x^2 - 1, 2)$ representing the (square minus 1) number for every point $(x^2, 0)$ representing a square number.

Also, because of [the interleave between square and oblong numbers](#) for every square number $(x^2, 0)$ there is an oblong number at $(x^2 + x, 1)$. Using the X axis as the base, these points are on a triangle (green side) of area with an odd value equal to the difference between the 2 consecutive squares.

In the smallest sums, for each square point $(x^2, -2x)$ there is a (square minus 1) point $(x^2 - 1, -2x)$. We highlight with orange ellipse.

Also, for each oblong point $(x^2 + x, -2x - 1)$ there is an (oblong minus 2) point $(x^2 + x - 2, -2x - 1)$. We highlight with brown ellipse.

These properties repeat along X-axis.

15.1 The SOM zones over the number line

Following the properties shown above, it is possible to divide the number line represented by the X-axis into an infinite sequence of 3 consecutive zones. Yellow is the S zone starting with square numbers, brown is the O zone starting with oblong numbers, and orange is the M zone starting with (square minus 1) numbers.

In this study, we will name each set of 3 consecutive zones as SOM zone.

Figure 76. The formation of SOM zones.

The first SOM zone for the positive numbers is 1,2,3. Then comes 4,6,8, followed by 9,12,15, and so on. They form the sequence <https://oeis.org/A006446>.

15.2 Covering the sums and differences with straight lines

All points representing [C000722](#) the smallest differences of the pairs of complementary divisors of the positive integers are covered by the straight lines in the form of $x = n * y + n^2$.

All points representing [C000724](#) the smallest sums of the pairs of complementary divisors of the positive integers are covered by the straight lines in the form of $x = -n * y - n^2$.

Figure 77. The straight lines $x = \pm n * y + n^2$ covering [C000722 \(A056737\)](#) the smallest differences in red.

See that the difference of the central complementary divisors of the negative square numbers $-x^2$ is $y = 2x$. These points the parabola $x = -\frac{y^2}{4}$ in red.

Figure 78. The straight lines $x = \pm n * y - n^2$ covering [C000724 \(A063655\)](#) the smallest sums in blue.

See that the sum of the central complementary divisors of the positive square numbers x^2 is $y = 2x$. These points the parabola $x = \frac{y^2}{4}$ in blue.

Figure 79. The straight lines $x = \pm n * y \pm n^2$ covering [C000722 \(A056737\)](#) the smallest differences in red, and covering [C000724 \(A063655\)](#) the smallest sums in blue.

15.3 Covering the sums and differences with parabolas lines

All points representing [C000722](#) the smallest differences of the pairs of complementary divisors of the positive integers in Q1 and Q2 are covered by parabola lines.

We use the parabola $x = -\frac{y^2}{4}$ as the square reference. It comes from [covering the differences with straight lines](#). This parabola covers the negative square differences. Negative square is $-x^2 = -x * x$. So, $d_{c1} = -x < d_{c2} = x$ and $b_{dm} = d_{c2} - d_{c1} = 2x$.

To cover all (*-square sequence + square numbers*) we need to add even squares. They are SUB-parabolas.

$$x = \frac{-y^2 + (2n)^2}{4} = \frac{-y^2 + (\text{even})^2}{4}$$

We use the parabola $x = -\frac{y^2+1}{4}$ as the oblong reference. This parabola covers the negative oblong differences. To cover all (*-oblong sequence + oblong numbers*) we need to add odd squares. They are in DES-parabolas.

$$x = \frac{-y^2 + (2n - 1)^2}{4} = \frac{-y^2 + (\text{odd})^2}{4}$$

Figure 80. The continuous SUB-parabolas lines in the form of $x = \frac{-y^2 + (2n)^2}{4} = \frac{-y^2 + (\text{even})^2}{4}$ and the dashed DES-parabolas lines in the form of $x = \frac{-y^2 + (2n - 1)^2}{4} = \frac{-y^2 + (\text{odd})^2}{4}$ covering [C000722 \(A056737\)](#) the smallest differences in red.

All points representing [C0007243](#) the smallest sums of the pairs of complementary divisors of the positive integers in Q3 and Q4 are covered by parabola lines.

We use the parabola $x = \frac{y^2}{4}$ as the square reference. It comes from [covering the differences with straight lines](#). This parabola covers the positive square sums. Positive square is $x^2 = -x * -x$. So, $d_{c1} = -x = d_{c2} = -x$ and $b_{am} = d_{c2} + d_{c1} = -2x$.

To cover all (*square sequence – square numbers*) we need to subtract even squares. They are SUB-parabolas.

$$x = \frac{y^2 - (2n)^2}{4} = \frac{y^2 - (even)^2}{4}$$

We use the parabola $x = \frac{y^2+1}{4}$ as the oblong reference. This parabola covers the positive oblong sums. To cover all (*oblong sequence – oblong numbers*) we need to subtract odd $\frac{squares}{4}$. They are in DES-parabolas.

$$x = \frac{y^2 - (2n - 1)^2}{4} = \frac{y^2 - (odd)^2}{4}$$

Figure 81. The continuous SUB-parabolas lines in the form of $x = \frac{y^2 - (2n)^2}{4} = \frac{y^2 - (\text{even})^2}{4}$ and the dashed DES-parabolas lines in the form of $x = \frac{y^2 - (2n-1)^2}{4} = \frac{y^2 - (\text{odd})^2}{4}$ covering [C000724 \(A063655\)](#) the smallest sums in blue.

Figure 82. The parabola lines $x = \frac{\pm y^2 \mp (2n)^2}{4} = \frac{\pm y^2 \mp (\text{even})^2}{4}$ covering [C000722 \(A056737\)](#) the smallest differences in red, and covering [C000724 \(A063655\)](#) the smallest sums in blue.

15.4 Quadratics using b_{dm}

When we say that $b_{dm} = d_{c2} - d_{c1}$, this means that all integers x with a constant value of b_{dm} , belong to the same quadratic sequence in the form of

$$x = d_{c1} * (d_{c1} + b_{dm}) = d_{c1}^2 + b_{dm} * d_{c1}$$

This quadratic has offset $f = \text{roundz} \left[-\frac{b_{dm}}{2} \right]$.

Or the quadratic sequence is in the form of:

$$x = d_{c2} * (d_{c2} - b_{dm}) = d_{c2}^2 - b_{dm} * d_{c2}$$

This quadratic has offset $f = \text{roundz} \left[\frac{b_{dm}}{2} \right]$.

In these cases, d_{c1} and d_{c2} are the index y and $\pm b_{dm}$ are the b coefficient of the quadratic equations.

If we set,

$$\begin{aligned} d_{c1} &= A033676[x] \\ d_{c2} &= A033677[x] \\ b_{dm} &= A056737[x] \end{aligned}$$

Then,

$$\begin{aligned} x &= A033676[x] * (A033676[x] + A056737[x]) \\ &= (A033676[x])^2 + A056737[x] * A033676[x] \\ x &= A033677[x] * (A033677[x] - A056737[x]) \\ &= (A033677[x])^2 - A056737[x] * A033677[x]. \end{aligned}$$

We can cover all integers with the above quadratic sequences by varying b_{dm} .

15.5 Quadratics using b_{sm}

Now, when we say that $b_{sm} = d_{c1} + d_{c2} = d_{c1} + (d_{c1} + b_{dm}) = 2d_{c1} + b_{dm}$, this means that integers x belong to the same quadratic sequence in the form of

$$\begin{aligned} x &= d_{c1} * d_{c2} \\ x &= d_{c1}(b_{sm} - d_{c1}) \\ x &= -d_{c1} * (d_{c1} - b_{sm}) = -d_{c1}^2 + b_{sm} * d_{c1} \end{aligned}$$

This quadratic has offset $f = \text{roundz} \left[\frac{b_{sm}}{2} \right]$.

If b_{dm} is even, then b_{sm} is even. If b_{dm} is odd, then b_{sm} is odd.

Or, in function of d_{c2} then $b_{sm} = d_{c2} + d_{c1} = d_{c2} + (d_{c2} - b_{dm}) = 2d_{c2} - b_{dm}$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} x &= d_{c2} * d_{c1} \\ x &= d_{c2}(b_{sm} - d_{c2}) \\ x &= -d_{c2} * (d_{c2} - b_{sm}) = -d_{c2}^2 + b_{sm} * d_{c2} \end{aligned}$$

This quadratic has offset $f = \text{roundz} \left[\frac{b_{sm}}{2} \right]$.

In these cases, d_{c1} and d_{c2} are the index y and only $+b_{sm}$ is the b coefficient of the quadratic equations.

If we set,

$$\begin{aligned} d_{c1} &= A033676[x] \\ d_{c2} &= A033677[x] \\ b_{sm} &= A063655[x] \end{aligned}$$

Then,

$$\begin{aligned} x &= -A033676[x] * (A033676[x] - A063655[x]) \\ &= -(A033676[x])^2 + A063655[x] * A033676[x] \\ A063655[x] &= 2 * A033676[x] + A056737[x] \end{aligned}$$

Or

$$\begin{aligned} x &= -A033677[x] * (A033677[x] - A063655[x]) \\ &= -(A033677[x])^2 + A063655[x] * A033677[x] \\ A063655[x] &= 2 * A033677[x] - A056737[x] \end{aligned}$$

We can cover all integers with the above quadratic sequences by varying b_{sm} .

15.6 Example for constant $b_{dm} = 8$:

Here are the 4 quadratic equations in table form for all the integers that have $b_{dm} = 8$:

A056737[x]				A063655[x]			
dc1	b _{dm}	dc2	x = dc1 * dc2	-dc1	b _{sm} =dc1+dc2	dc1 - b _{sm}	-dc1(dc1-b _{sm})
Index	b _{dm} =dc2-dc1	dc1 + b _{dm}	dc1(dc1+b _{dm})	2*dc1 + b _{dm}	dc1 - b _{sm}	-dc1(dc1-b _{sm})	
-10	8	-2	20	10	-12	2	20
-9	8	-1	9	9	-10	1	9
-8	8	0	0	8	-8	0	0
-7	8	1	-7	7	-6	-1	-7
-6	8	2	-12	6	-4	-2	-12
-5	8	3	-15	5	-2	-3	-15
-4	8	4	-16	4	0	-4	-16
-3	8	5	-15	3	2	-5	-15
-2	8	6	-12	2	4	-6	-12
-1	8	7	-7	1	6	-7	-7
0	8	8	0	0	8	-8	0
1	8	9	9	-1	10	-9	9
2	8	10	20	-2	12	-10	20
3	8	11	33	-3	14	-11	33
4	8	12	48	-4	16	-12	48
5	8	13	65	-5	18	-13	65
6	8	14	84	-6	20	-14	84
7	8	15	105	-7	22	-15	105
8	8	16	128	-8	24	-16	128
9	8	17	153	-9	26	-17	153
10	8	18	180	-10	28	-18	180

A056737[x]				A063655[x]			
dc2	b _{dm}	dc1	x = dc2 * dc1	-dc2	b _{sm} =dc1+dc2	dc2 - b _{sm}	-dc2(dc2-b _{sm})
Index	b _{dm} =dc2-dc1	dc2 - b _{dm}	dc2(dc2-b _{dm})	2*dc2 - b _{dm}	dc2 - b _{sm}	-dc2(dc2-b _{sm})	
-10	8	-18	180	10	-28	18	180
-9	8	-17	153	9	-26	17	153
-8	8	-16	128	8	-24	16	128
-7	8	-15	105	7	-22	15	105
-6	8	-14	84	6	-20	14	84
-5	8	-13	65	5	-18	13	65
-4	8	-12	48	4	-16	12	48
-3	8	-11	33	3	-14	11	33
-2	8	-10	20	2	-12	10	20
-1	8	-9	9	1	-10	9	9
0	8	-8	0	0	-8	8	0
1	8	-7	-7	-1	-6	7	-7
2	8	-6	-12	-2	-4	6	-12
3	8	-5	-15	-3	-2	5	-15
4	8	-4	-16	-4	0	4	-16
5	8	-3	-15	-5	2	3	-15
6	8	-2	-12	-6	4	2	-12
7	8	-1	-7	-7	6	1	-7
8	8	0	0	-8	8	0	0
9	8	1	9	-9	10	-1	9
10	8	2	20	-10	12	-2	20

Figure 83. The quadratics producing integers with $b_{dm} = 8$.

There are 4 similar tables. In all, the 1st and 3rd column are the divisors of the product $x = d_{c1} * d_{c2} = d_{c2} * d_{c1}$ in the 5th column. The 2nd column in red is the smallest difference b_{dm} <https://oeis.org/A056737> and in blue is the smallest sum b_{sm} <https://oeis.org/A063655>.

When we linearly vary one of the divisors, then it becomes our index of the quadratic equation. They are in the first column.

The first top table is the quadratic $x = y(y + b_{dm}) = y(y + 8)$. For each possible $d_{c1} = y$, we calculate $d_{c2} = (y + 8)$.

The first bottom table is the quadratic $x = y(y - b_{dm}) = y(y - 8)$. For each possible $d_{c2} = y$, we calculate $d_{c1} = (y - 8)$.

The second top and tables are the same form of quadratic $x = -y(y - b_{sm})$. For each possible $d_{c1} = -y$, we calculate $d_{c2} = y - b_{sm}$. In the second top table $b_{sm} = 2y + b_{dm} = 2y + 8$. In the second bottom table $b_{sm} = 2y - b_{dm} = 2y - 8$.

In all the 4 tables the sequence is the elements from the products $x = d_{c1} * d_{c2} = d_{c2} * d_{c1}$.

The result is only one sequence <https://oeis.org/A028566>. The only difference is the offset between them.

As a direct consequence, we will expand this recurring reasoning/algorithm.

15.7 Quadratic in the form of $b_{dm} = 0$

We can express integers in the form of $x = y(y + 0)$ substituting $y = z - 0$ resulting in $x = (z - 0)(z - 0 + 0) = z * z = z^2$. These integers belong to the sequence <https://oeis.org/A000290>.

Once y can be either $A033676[x]$ or $A033677[x]$, then let us call the quadratic sequence of the numbers in the form of $y(y \pm A056737)$ for $A056737[x] = 0$ or in the form of $-y(y - A063655[x])$ for $A063655[x] = 2y \pm A056737[x] = 2y \pm 0$ as the "square minus 0" sequence.

Figure 84. The quadratics producing integers with $b_{dm} = 0$.

15.8 Quadratic in the form of $b_{dm} = 1$

We can express integers in the form of $x = y(y + 1)$ substituting $y = z - 0$ resulting in $x = (z - 0)(z - 0 + 1) = z(z + 1) = z^2 + z$. These integers belong to the sequence <https://oeis.org/A002378>.

Once y can be either $A033676[x]$ or $A033677[x]$, then let us call the quadratic sequence of the numbers in the form of $y(y \pm A056737)$ for $A056737[x] = 1$ or in the form of $-y(y - A063655[x])$ for $A063655[x] = 2y \pm A056737[x] = 2y \pm 1$ as the "oblong minus 0" sequence.

A056737[x]				A063655[x]			
dc1	bdm	dc2	x = dc1 * dc2	-dc1	2*dc1 + bdm	dc1 - bsm	-dc1(dc1-bsm)
Index	bdm=dc2-dc1	dc1 + bdm	dc1(dc1+bdm)				
-10	1	-9	90	10	-19	9	90
-9	1	-8	72	9	-17	8	72
-8	1	-7	56	8	-15	7	56
-7	1	-6	42	7	-13	6	42
-6	1	-5	30	6	-11	5	30
-5	1	-4	20	5	-9	4	20
-4	1	-3	12	4	-7	3	12
-3	1	-2	6	3	-5	2	6
-2	1	-1	2	2	-3	1	2
-1	1	0	0	1	-1	0	0
0	1	1	0	0	1	-1	0
1	1	2	2	-1	3	-2	2
2	1	3	6	-2	5	-3	6
3	1	4	12	-3	7	-4	12
4	1	5	20	-4	9	-5	20
5	1	6	30	-5	11	-6	30
6	1	7	42	-6	13	-7	42
7	1	8	56	-7	15	-8	56
8	1	9	72	-8	17	-9	72
9	1	10	90	-9	19	-10	90
10	1	11	110	-10	21	-11	110

A056737[x]				A063655[x]			
dc2	bdm	dc1	x = dc2 * dc1	-dc2	2*dc2 - bdm	dc2 - bsm	-dc2(dc2-bsm)
Index	bdm=dc2-dc1	dc2 - bdm	dc2(dc2-bdm)				
-10	1	-11	110	10	-21	11	110
-9	1	-10	90	9	-19	10	90
-8	1	-9	72	8	-17	9	72
-7	1	-8	56	7	-15	8	56
-6	1	-7	42	6	-13	7	42
-5	1	-6	30	5	-11	6	30
-4	1	-5	20	4	-9	5	20
-3	1	-4	12	3	-7	4	12
-2	1	-3	6	2	-5	3	6
-1	1	-2	2	1	-3	2	2
0	1	-1	0	0	-1	1	0
1	1	0	0	-1	1	0	0
2	1	1	2	-2	3	-1	2
3	1	2	6	-3	5	-2	6
4	1	3	12	-4	7	-3	12
5	1	4	20	-5	9	-4	20
6	1	5	30	-6	11	-5	30
7	1	6	42	-7	13	-6	42
8	1	7	56	-8	15	-7	56
9	1	8	72	-9	17	-8	72
10	1	9	90	-10	19	-9	90

Figure 85. The quadratics producing integers with $b_{dm} = 1$.

15.9 Quadratic in the form of $b_{dm} = 2$

We can express integers in the form of $x = y(y + 2)$ substituting $y = z - 1$ resulting in $x = (z - 1)(z - 1 + 2) = (z - 1)(z + 1) = z^2 - 1$. These integers belong to the sequence <https://oeis.org/A005563>.

Once y can be either $A033676[x]$ or $A033677[x]$, then let us call the quadratic sequence of the numbers in the form of $y(y \pm A056737)$ for $A056737[x] = 2$ or in the form of

$-y(y - A063655[x])$ for $A063655[x] = 2y \pm A056737[x] = 2y \pm 2$ as the "square minus 1" sequence.

A056737[x]				A063655[x]			
dc1	b _{dm}	dc2	x = dc1 * dc2	-dc1	bsm=dc1+dc2	dc1 - bsm	-dc1(dc1-bsm)
Index	b _{dm} =dc2-dc1	dc1 + b _{dm}	dc1(dc1+b _{dm})	2*dc1 + b _{dm}	dc1 - bsm	-dc1(dc1-bsm)	
-10	2	-8	80	10	-18	8	80
-9	2	-7	63	9	-16	7	63
-8	2	-6	48	8	-14	6	48
-7	2	-5	35	7	-12	5	35
-6	2	-4	24	6	-10	4	24
-5	2	-3	15	5	-8	3	15
-4	2	-2	8	4	-6	2	8
-3	2	-1	3	3	-4	1	3
-2	2	0	0	2	-2	0	0
-1	2	1	-1	1	0	-1	-1
0	2	2	0	0	2	-2	0
1	2	3	3	-1	4	-3	3
2	2	4	8	-2	6	-4	8
3	2	5	15	-3	8	-5	15
4	2	6	24	-4	10	-6	24
5	2	7	35	-5	12	-7	35
6	2	8	48	-6	14	-8	48
7	2	9	63	-7	16	-9	63
8	2	10	80	-8	18	-10	80
9	2	11	99	-9	20	-11	99
10	2	12	120	-10	22	-12	120

A056737[x]				A063655[x]			
dc2	b _{dm}	dc1	x = dc2 * dc1	-dc2	bsm=dc2+dc1	dc2 - bsm	-dc2(dc2-bsm)
Index	b _{dm} =dc2-dc1	dc2 - b _{dm}	dc2(dc2-b _{dm})	2*dc2 - b _{dm}	dc2 - bsm	-dc2(dc2-bsm)	
-10	2	-12	120	10	-22	12	120
-9	2	-11	99	9	-20	11	99
-8	2	-10	80	8	-18	10	80
-7	2	-9	63	7	-16	9	63
-6	2	-8	48	6	-14	8	48
-5	2	-7	35	5	-12	7	35
-4	2	-6	24	4	-10	6	24
-3	2	-5	15	3	-8	5	15
-2	2	-4	8	2	-6	4	8
-1	2	-3	3	1	-4	3	3
0	2	-2	0	0	-2	2	0
1	2	-1	-1	-1	0	1	-1
2	2	0	0	-2	2	0	0
3	2	1	3	-3	4	-1	3
4	2	2	8	-4	6	-2	8
5	2	3	15	-5	8	-3	15
6	2	4	24	-6	10	-4	24
7	2	5	35	-7	12	-5	35
8	2	6	48	-8	14	-6	48
9	2	7	63	-9	16	-7	63
10	2	8	80	-10	18	-8	80

Figure 86. The quadratics producing integers with $b_{dm} = 2$.

15.10 Quadratic in the form of $b_{dm} = 3$

We can express integers in the form of $x = y(y + 3)$ substituting $y = z - 1$ resulting in $x = (z - 1)(z - 1 + 3) = (z - 1)(z + 2) = z^2 + z - 2$. These integers belong to the sequence <https://oeis.org/A028552>.

Once y can be either $A033676[x]$ or $A033677[x]$, then let us call the quadratic sequence of the numbers in the form of $y(y \pm A056737)$ for $A056737[x] = 3$ or in the form of $-y(y - A063655[x])$ for $A063655[x] = 2y \pm A056737[x] = 2y \pm 3$ as the "oblong minus 2" sequence.

A056737[x]				A063655[x]			
dc1	b _{dm}	dc2	x = dc1 * dc2	-dc1	bsm=dc1+dc2	dc1 - bsm	-dc1(dc1-bsm)
Index	b _{dm} =dc2-dc1	dc1 + b _{dm}	dc1(dc1+b _{dm})	2*dc1 + b _{dm}	dc1 - bsm	-dc1(dc1-bsm)	
-10	3	-7	70	10	-17	7	70
-9	3	-6	54	9	-15	6	54
-8	3	-5	40	8	-13	5	40
-7	3	-4	28	7	-11	4	28
-6	3	-3	18	6	-9	3	18
-5	3	-2	10	5	-7	2	10
-4	3	-1	4	4	-5	1	4
-3	3	0	0	3	-3	0	0
-2	3	1	-2	2	-1	-1	-2
-1	3	2	-2	1	1	-2	-2
0	3	3	0	0	3	-3	0
1	3	4	4	-1	5	-4	4
2	3	5	10	-2	7	-5	10
3	3	6	18	-3	9	-6	18
4	3	7	28	-4	11	-7	28
5	3	8	40	-5	13	-8	40
6	3	9	54	-6	15	-9	54
7	3	10	70	-7	17	-10	70
8	3	11	88	-8	19	-11	88
9	3	12	108	-9	21	-12	108
10	3	13	130	-10	23	-13	130

A056737[x]				A063655[x]			
dc2	b _{dm}	dc1	x = dc2 * dc1	-dc2	bsm=dc2+dc1	dc2 - bsm	-dc2(dc2-bsm)
Index	b _{dm} =dc2-dc1	dc2 - b _{dm}	dc2(dc2-b _{dm})	2*dc2 - b _{dm}	dc2 - bsm	-dc2(dc2-bsm)	
-10	3	-13	130	10	-23	13	130
-9	3	-12	108	9	-21	12	108
-8	3	-11	88	8	-19	11	88
-7	3	-10	70	7	-17	10	70
-6	3	-9	54	6	-15	9	54
-5	3	-8	40	5	-13	8	40
-4	3	-7	28	4	-11	7	28
-3	3	-6	18	3	-9	6	18
-2	3	-5	10	2	-7	5	10
-1	3	-4	4	1	-5	4	4
0	3	-3	0	0	-3	3	0
1	3	-2	-2	-1	-1	2	-2
2	3	-1	-2	-2	1	1	-2
3	3	0	0	-3	3	0	0
4	3	1	4	-4	5	-1	4
5	3	2	10	-5	7	-2	10
6	3	3	18	-6	9	-3	18
7	3	4	28	-7	11	-4	28
8	3	5	40	-8	13	-5	40
9	3	6	54	-9	15	-6	54
10	3	7	70	-10	17	-7	70

Figure 87. The quadratics producing integers with $b_{dm} = 3$.

15.11 Quadratic in the form of $b_{dm} = 4$

We can express integers in the form of $x = y(y + 4)$ substituting $y = z - 2$ resulting in $x = (z - 2)(z - 2 + 4) = (z - 2)(z + 2) = z^2 - 4$. These integers belong to the sequence <https://oeis.org/A028347>.

Once y can be either $A033676[x]$ or $A033677[x]$, then let us call the quadratic sequence of the numbers in the form of $y(y \pm A056737)$ for $A056737[x] = 4$ or in the form of $-y(y - A063655[x])$ for $A063655[x] = 2y \pm A056737[x] = 2y \pm 4$ as the "square minus 4" sequence.

A056737[x]				A063655[x]			
dc1	bdm	dc2	x = dc1 * dc2	-dc1	bsm=dc1+dc2	dc1 - bsm	-dc1(dc1-bsm)
Index	bdm=dc2-dc1	dc1 + bdm	dc1(dc1+bdm)	2*dc1 + bdm	dc1 - bsm	-dc1(dc1-bsm)	
-10	4	-6	60	10	-16	6	60
-9	4	-5	45	9	-14	5	45
-8	4	-4	32	8	-12	4	32
-7	4	-3	21	7	-10	3	21
-6	4	-2	12	6	-8	2	12
-5	4	-1	5	5	-6	1	5
-4	4	0	0	4	-4	0	0
-3	4	1	-3	3	-2	-1	-3
-2	4	2	-4	2	0	-2	-4
-1	4	3	-3	1	2	-3	-3
0	4	4	0	0	4	-4	0
1	4	5	5	-1	6	-5	5
2	4	6	12	-2	8	-6	12
3	4	7	21	-3	10	-7	21
4	4	8	32	-4	12	-8	32
5	4	9	45	-5	14	-9	45
6	4	10	60	-6	16	-10	60
7	4	11	77	-7	18	-11	77
8	4	12	96	-8	20	-12	96
9	4	13	117	-9	22	-13	117
10	4	14	140	-10	24	-14	140

A056737[x]				A063655[x]			
dc2	bdm	dc1	x = dc2 * dc1	-dc2	bsm=dc2+dc1	dc2 - bsm	-dc2(dc2-bsm)
Index	bdm=dc2-dc1	dc2 - bdm	dc2(dc2-bdm)	2*dc2 - bdm	dc2 - bsm	-dc2(dc2-bsm)	
-10	4	-14	140	10	-24	14	140
-9	4	-13	117	9	-22	13	117
-8	4	-12	96	8	-20	12	96
-7	4	-11	77	7	-18	11	77
-6	4	-10	60	6	-16	10	60
-5	4	-9	45	5	-14	9	45
-4	4	-8	32	4	-12	8	32
-3	4	-7	21	3	-10	7	21
-2	4	-6	12	2	-8	6	12
-1	4	-5	5	1	-6	5	5
0	4	-4	0	0	-4	4	0
1	4	-3	-3	-1	-2	3	-3
2	4	-2	-4	-2	0	2	-4
3	4	-1	-3	-3	2	1	-3
4	4	0	0	-4	4	0	0
5	4	1	5	-5	6	-1	5
6	4	2	12	-6	8	-2	12
7	4	3	21	-7	10	-3	21
8	4	4	32	-8	12	-4	32
9	4	5	45	-9	14	-5	45
10	4	6	60	-10	16	-6	60

Figure 88. The quadratics producing integers with $b_{dm} = 4$.

15.12 Quadratic in the form of $b_{dm} = 5$

We can express integers in the form of $x = y(y + 5)$ substituting $y = z - 2$ resulting in $x = (z - 2)(z - 2 + 5) = (z - 2)(z + 3) = z^2 + z - 6$. These integers belong to the sequence <https://oeis.org/A028557>.

Once y can be either $A033676[x]$ or $A033677[x]$, then let us call the quadratic sequence of the numbers in the form of $y(y \pm A056737)$ for $A056737[x] = 5$ or in the form of $-y(y - A063655[x])$ for $A063655[x] = 2y \pm A056737[x] = 2y \pm 5$ as the "oblong minus 6" sequence.

A056737[x]				A063655[x]			
dc1	bdm	dc2	x = dc1 * dc2	-dc1	bsm=dc1+dc2	dc1 - bsm	-dc1(dc1-bsm)
Index	bdm=dc2-dc1	dc1 + bdm	dc1(dc1+bdm)	2*dc1 + bdm	dc1 - bsm	-dc1(dc1-bsm)	
-10	5	-5	50	10	-15	5	50
-9	5	-4	36	9	-13	4	36
-8	5	-3	24	8	-11	3	24
-7	5	-2	14	7	-9	2	14
-6	5	-1	6	6	-7	1	6
-5	5	0	0	5	-5	0	0
-4	5	1	-4	4	-3	-1	-4
-3	5	2	-6	3	-1	-2	-6
-2	5	3	-6	2	1	-3	-6
-1	5	4	-4	1	3	-4	-4
0	5	5	0	0	5	-5	0
1	5	6	6	-1	7	-6	6
2	5	7	14	-2	9	-7	14
3	5	8	24	-3	11	-8	24
4	5	9	36	-4	13	-9	36
5	5	10	50	-5	15	-10	50
6	5	11	66	-6	17	-11	66
7	5	12	84	-7	19	-12	84
8	5	13	104	-8	21	-13	104
9	5	14	126	-9	23	-14	126
10	5	15	150	-10	25	-15	150

A056737[x]				A063655[x]			
dc2	bdm	dc1	x = dc2 * dc1	-dc2	bsm=dc2+dc1	dc2 - bsm	-dc2(dc2-bsm)
Index	bdm=dc2-dc1	dc2 - bdm	dc2(dc2-bdm)	2*dc2 - bdm	dc2 - bsm	-dc2(dc2-bsm)	
-10	5	-15	150	10	-25	15	150
-9	5	-14	126	9	-23	14	126
-8	5	-13	104	8	-21	13	104
-7	5	-12	84	7	-19	12	84
-6	5	-11	66	6	-17	11	66
-5	5	-10	50	5	-15	10	50
-4	5	-9	36	4	-13	9	36
-3	5	-8	24	3	-11	8	24
-2	5	-7	14	2	-9	7	14
-1	5	-6	6	1	-7	6	6
0	5	-5	0	0	-5	5	0
1	5	-4	-4	-1	-3	4	-4
2	5	-3	-6	-2	-1	3	-6
3	5	-2	-6	-3	1	2	-6
4	5	-1	-4	-4	3	1	-4
5	5	0	0	-5	5	0	0
6	5	1	6	-6	7	-1	6
7	5	2	14	-7	9	-2	14
8	5	3	24	-8	11	-3	24
9	5	4	36	-9	13	-4	36
10	5	5	50	-10	15	-5	50

Figure 89. The quadratics producing integers with $b_{dm} = 5$.

15.13 Quadratic in the form of $b_{dm} = 6$

We can express integers in the form of $x = y(y + 6)$ substituting $y = z - 3$ resulting in $x = (z - 3)(z - 3 + 6) = (z - 3)(z + 3) = z^2 - 9$. These integers belong to the sequence <https://oeis.org/A028560>.

Once y can be either $A033676[x]$ or $A033677[x]$, then let us call the quadratic sequence of the numbers in the form of $y(y \pm A056737)$ for $A056737[x] = 6$ or in the form of $-y(y - A063655[x])$ for $A063655[x] = 2y \pm A056737[x] = 2y \pm 6$ as the "square minus 9" sequence.

A056737[x]				A063655[x]			
dc1	bdm	dc2	x = dc1 * dc2	-dc1	bsm=dc1+dc2	dc1 - bsm	-dc1(dc1-bsm)
Index	bdm=dc2-dc1	dc1 + bdm	dc1(dc1+bdm)	2*dc1 + bdm	dc1 - bsm	-dc1(dc1-bsm)	
-10	6	-4	40	10	-14	4	40
-9	6	-3	27	9	-12	3	27
-8	6	-2	16	8	-10	2	16
-7	6	-1	7	7	-8	1	7
-6	6	0	0	6	-6	0	0
-5	6	1	-5	5	-4	-1	-5
-4	6	2	-8	4	-2	-2	-8
-3	6	3	-9	3	0	-3	-9
-2	6	4	-8	2	2	-4	-8
-1	6	5	-5	1	4	-5	-5
0	6	6	0	0	6	-6	0
1	6	7	7	-1	8	-7	7
2	6	8	16	-2	10	-8	16
3	6	9	27	-3	12	-9	27
4	6	10	40	-4	14	-10	40
5	6	11	55	-5	16	-11	55
6	6	12	72	-6	18	-12	72
7	6	13	91	-7	20	-13	91
8	6	14	112	-8	22	-14	112
9	6	15	135	-9	24	-15	135
10	6	16	160	-10	26	-16	160

A056737[x]				A063655[x]			
dc2	bdm	dc1	x = dc2 * dc1	-dc2	bsm=dc2+dc1	dc2 - bsm	-dc2(dc2-bsm)
Index	bdm=dc2-dc1	dc2 - bdm	dc2(dc2-bdm)	2*dc2 - bdm	dc2 - bsm	-dc2(dc2-bsm)	
-10	6	-16	160	10	-26	16	160
-9	6	-15	135	9	-24	15	135
-8	6	-14	112	8	-22	14	112
-7	6	-13	91	7	-20	13	91
-6	6	-12	72	6	-18	12	72
-5	6	-11	55	5	-16	11	55
-4	6	-10	40	4	-14	10	40
-3	6	-9	27	3	-12	9	27
-2	6	-8	16	2	-10	8	16
-1	6	-7	7	1	-8	7	7
0	6	-6	0	0	-6	6	0
1	6	-5	-5	-1	-4	5	-5
2	6	-4	-8	-2	-2	4	-8
3	6	-3	-9	-3	0	3	-9
4	6	-2	-8	-4	2	2	-8
5	6	-1	-5	-5	4	1	-5
6	6	0	0	-6	6	0	0
7	6	1	7	-7	8	-1	7
8	6	2	16	-8	10	-2	16
9	6	3	27	-9	12	-3	27
10	6	4	40	-10	14	-4	40

Figure 90. The quadratics producing integers with $b_{dm} = 6$.

15.14 Quadratic in the form of $b_{dm} = 7$

We can express integers in the form of $x = y(y + 7)$ substituting $y = z - 3$ resulting in $x = (z - 3)(z - 3 + 7) = (z - 3)(z + 4) = z^2 + z - 12$. These integers belong to the sequence <https://oeis.org/A028563>.

Once y can be either $A033676[x]$ or $A033677[x]$, then let us call the quadratic sequence of the numbers in the form of $y(y \pm A056737)$ for $A056737[x] = 7$ or in the form of $-y(y - A063655[x])$ for $A063655[x] = 2y \pm A056737[x] = 2y \pm 7$ as the "oblong minus 12" sequence.

A056737[x]				A063655[x]			
dc1	b _{dm}	dc2	x = dc1 * dc2	-dc1	bsm=dc1+dc2	dc1 - bsm	-dc1(dc1-bsm)
Index	b _{dm} =dc2-dc1	dc1 + b _{dm}	dc1(dc1+b _{dm})	2*dc1 + b _{dm}	dc1 - bsm	-dc1(dc1-bsm)	
-10	7	-3	30	10	-13	3	30
-9	7	-2	18	9	-11	2	18
-8	7	-1	8	8	-9	1	8
-7	7	0	0	7	-7	0	0
-6	7	1	-6	6	-5	-1	-6
-5	7	2	-10	5	-3	-2	-10
-4	7	3	-12	4	-1	-3	-12
-3	7	4	-12	3	1	-4	-12
-2	7	5	-10	2	3	-5	-10
-1	7	6	-6	1	5	-6	-6
0	7	7	0	0	7	-7	0
1	7	8	8	-1	9	-8	8
2	7	9	18	-2	11	-9	18
3	7	10	30	-3	13	-10	30
4	7	11	44	-4	15	-11	44
5	7	12	60	-5	17	-12	60
6	7	13	78	-6	19	-13	78
7	7	14	98	-7	21	-14	98
8	7	15	120	-8	23	-15	120
9	7	16	144	-9	25	-16	144
10	7	17	170	-10	27	-17	170

A056737[x]				A063655[x]			
dc2	b _{dm}	dc1	x = dc2 * dc1	-dc2	bsm=dc2+dc1	dc2 - bsm	-dc2(dc2-bsm)
Index	b _{dm} =dc2-dc1	dc2 - b _{dm}	dc2(dc2-b _{dm})	2*dc2 - b _{dm}	dc2 - bsm	-dc2(dc2-bsm)	
-10	7	-17	170	10	-27	17	170
-9	7	-16	144	9	-25	16	144
-8	7	-15	120	8	-23	15	120
-7	7	-14	98	7	-21	14	98
-6	7	-13	78	6	-19	13	78
-5	7	-12	60	5	-17	12	60
-4	7	-11	44	4	-15	11	44
-3	7	-10	30	3	-13	10	30
-2	7	-9	18	2	-11	9	18
-1	7	-8	8	1	-9	8	8
0	7	-7	0	0	-7	7	0
1	7	-6	-6	-1	-5	6	-6
2	7	-5	-10	-2	-3	5	-10
3	7	-4	-12	-3	-1	4	-12
4	7	-3	-12	-4	1	3	-12
5	7	-2	-10	-5	3	2	-10
6	7	-1	-6	-6	5	1	-6
7	7	0	0	-7	7	0	0
8	7	1	8	-8	9	-1	8
9	7	2	18	-9	11	-2	18
10	7	3	30	-10	13	-3	30

Figure 91. The quadratics producing integers with $b_{dm} = 7$.

15.15 Generalizing:

We can continue increasing b_{dm} indefinitely.

We can express integers in the form of $x = y(y + even)$ substituting $y = z - \left(\frac{even}{2}\right)$ resulting in $x = \left(z - \frac{even}{2}\right)\left(z + \frac{even}{2}\right) = z^2 - \left(\frac{even}{2}\right)^2 = square\ sequence - square\ number$.

Once y can be either [A033676\[x\]](#) or [A033677\[x\]](#), then let us call the quadratic sequence of the numbers in the form of $y(y \pm b_{dm})$ for $b_{dm} = \text{A056737}[x] = even$ or in the form of $-y(y - b_{sm})$ for $b_{sm} = 2y \pm b_{dm}$ as the as the “square sequence [A000290](#) minus a square number $\left(\frac{even}{2}\right)^2$ ”.

We can express integers in the form of $x = y(y + odd)$ substituting $y = z - \frac{odd-1}{2}$ resulting in $x = \left(z - \frac{odd-1}{2}\right)\left(z + \frac{odd+1}{2}\right) = z^2 + z - \left(\frac{odd-1}{2}\right)\left(\frac{odd+1}{2}\right)$.

Once y can be either [A033676\[x\]](#) or [A033677\[x\]](#), then let us call the quadratic sequence of the numbers in the form of $y(y \pm b_m)$ for $b_m = \text{A056737}[x] = odd$ or in the form of $-y(y -$

b_{sm}) for $b_{sm} = 2y \pm b_{dm}$ the “oblong sequence [A002378](#) minus an oblong number $\left(\frac{odd-1}{2}\right)\left(\frac{odd+1}{2}\right)$ ”.

15.16 The Quadratic Composite Generators

See below the table of equivalence of the first 32 sequences in the OEIS. We have a column with hyperbolic equations and two columns with quadratic equations, where one has offset not zero and the other offset zero.

The equations in each row always generate the same sequence. Changes only the offset:

$b_{dm} =$ A056737	OEIS	Name	CG equation in offset f		CG equation $f = 0$
0	https://oeis.org/A000290	square-0	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 0)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 0y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 0$
1	https://oeis.org/A002378	oblong-0	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 1)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 1y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 0$
2	https://oeis.org/A005563	square-1	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 2)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 2y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 1$
3	https://oeis.org/A028552	oblong-2	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 3)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 3y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 2$
4	https://oeis.org/A028347	square-4	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 4)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 4y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 4$
5	https://oeis.org/A028557	oblong-6	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 5)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 5y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 6$
6	https://oeis.org/A028560	square-9	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 6)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 6y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 9$
7	https://oeis.org/A028563	oblong-12	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 7)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 7y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 12$
8	https://oeis.org/A028566	square-16	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 8)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 8y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 16$
9	https://oeis.org/A028569	oblong-20	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 9)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 9y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 20$
10	https://oeis.org/A098603	square-25	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 10)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 10y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 25$
11	https://oeis.org/A119412	oblong-30	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 11)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 11y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 30$
12	https://oeis.org/A098847	square-36	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 12)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 12y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 36$
13	https://oeis.org/A132759	oblong-42	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 13)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 13y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 42$
14	https://oeis.org/A098848	square-49	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 14)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 14y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 49$
15	https://oeis.org/A132760	oblong-56	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 15)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 15y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 56$
16	https://oeis.org/A098849	square-64	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 16)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 16y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 64$
17	https://oeis.org/A132761	oblong-72	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 17)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 17y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 72$
18	https://oeis.org/A098850	square-81	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 18)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 18y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 81$
19	https://oeis.org/A132762	oblong-90	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 19)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 19y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 90$
20	https://oeis.org/A120071	square-100	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 20)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 20y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 100$
21	https://oeis.org/A132763	oblong-110	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 21)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 21y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 110$
22	https://oeis.org/A132764	square-121	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 22)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 22y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 121$
23	https://oeis.org/A132765	oblong-132	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 23)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 23y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 132$
24	https://oeis.org/A132766	square-144	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 24)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 24y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 144$
25	https://oeis.org/A132767	oblong-156	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 25)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 25y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 156$
26	https://oeis.org/A132768	square-169	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 26)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 26y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 169$
27	https://oeis.org/A132769	oblong-182	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 27)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 27y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 182$
28	https://oeis.org/A132770	square-196	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 28)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 28y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 196$
29	https://oeis.org/A132771	oblong-210	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 29)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 29y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 210$
30	https://oeis.org/A132772	square-225	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 30)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 30y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 225$
31	https://oeis.org/A132773	oblong-240	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 31)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 31y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 240$

Figure 92. Quadratic Composite Generators table showing the initial sequences in the form of (square sequence – square number) and (oblong sequence – oblong number).

The interleaving between the square numbers and the oblong numbers is the sequence <https://oeis.org/A002620>.

The quadratic composite generators are the diagonals in the MT – Multiplication table[11].

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Conflicts of Interest

The author declare no conflicts of interest.

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